

Report on the implementation of the action
Call for proposals –
EP-COMM-SUBV-NAT-E-2023

1 GRANT AGREEMENT ID:
PO 3200002745
2. AMENDMENT(S):
Please indicate the number, reference and object of the amendments already approved by the European Parliament. Click or tap here to enter text.
3. BENEFICIARY:
Universitat de Barcelona, Spain. Coord. Mihaela Vancea (mihaela.vancea@ub.edu)
4. TITLE OF THE ACTION:
Fostering Youth Participation in the EE24: Informing, Debating, Acting (ActiveYouth_EE24)
5. ACTION CATEGORY:
Please select one action category Category 1 - Civil society engagement actions (point 2.2.1 of the call for proposals)
6. DURATION OF THE ACTION:
from 01/02/2024 (“starting date”) until 30/06/2024 (“end date”)
7. SUMMARY OF THE ACTION
<i>Please briefly describe the context and overall objective, the target audiences, the activities performed and the countries where those activities took place and main achievements; the results and impact in a stand-alone text to give readers a clear idea of what the project is about. The EP may publish this summary for dissemination purposes, do not include any confidential information or personal data. Diagrams or photographs illustrating the work of the project can be included but only as images and for which you have the rights.</i> Despite the rising trend in voter turnout among young adults in the 2019 European Parliament elections, significant disparities persist in their knowledge and engagement with European institutions and politics. Many young adults lack a comprehensive understanding of how European Parliament elections operate and how the resulting decisions impact their lives and career opportunities. To address these challenges, the ActiveYouth_EE24 project was developed. This initiative combines a comprehensive student survey, an open event, several seminars debating an informative dossier on European institutions and elections, and a targeted student-led communication campaign to bridge the knowledge gap. Its primary objective was to enhance the participation of Catalan students in the 2024 European Parliament Elections by equipping them with critical information, fostering informed debate, and encouraging proactive involvement.

Through these efforts, ActiveYouth_EE24 aimed to create a more informed, engaged, and active youth electorate for the upcoming elections. The main results show that promoting greater engagement and knowledge about elections and European institutions among university students is essential to ensure effective and responsible representation of their interests. Moreover, students' engagement and direct participation in pre-electoral communication activities proved to be extremely fruitful in creating a more informed and motivated young electorate.

8. IMPLEMENTATION OF THE ACTION

a) General and specific objectives achieved

Please explain the general and specific objectives of the action that have been achieved. Please detail the objectives that have been partially achieved and/or not at all achieved and explain the reasons why.

The ActiveYouth_EE24 project had a threefold objective:

- (1) To identify with precision UB students' level of knowledge and perception about European institutions and elections.
- (2) To contribute to the formation of an informed opinion among them about the significance of the EP for shaping better life opportunities for young Catalan population; and
- (3) To increase Catalan youth participation in the EE24 and their involvement in the together.eu community.

To nurture an informed opinion of students in Catalonia about the role and democratic values of the European Parliament (EP) and the European Union (EU), as well as to promote their involvement and active participation in the European Elections 2024 (EE24), various specific objectives were considered. In the following, we address each specific objective separately explaining their degree of achievement.

Specific Objective 1. To identify UB university students' level of knowledge and perception about the role of the EP and the importance of European Parliament elections in their lives

This objective has been largely achieved. The survey was intended to inform the development of the informative dossier. However, due to the sign-off delay of the grant agreement and the survey assessment process by the UB ethics committee, the survey was implemented after the development and presentation of the informative dossier to the student population. Ultimately, this strategy proved to be successful, as it allowed us to better prepare the presentation and dissemination of the survey results to the target audience. Additionally, it facilitated the introduction and implementation of the survey with the student population.

The survey results provide valuable and clear information not only about UB students' knowledge of European institutions and elections but also about the frequency of information, level of interest, participation, and individual assessments and opinions. A more accurate analysis in terms of the objective's fulfilment follows below:

- The survey significantly exceeded its initial goal of reaching at least 150 students from three faculties of the University of Barcelona (UB): the Faculty of Education, the Faculty of Information and Audiovisual Media, and the Faculty of Law. The Faculty of Law came to replace the initially proposed Faculty of Economics and Business as the research member involved from this faculty has changed his institutional adscription before the starting of the project. Notably, the total survey sample included 349 responses from students across different Catalan universities. Within these three faculties, there were 233 responses distributed as follows: 104 from the Faculty of Education, 78 from the Faculty of Information and Audiovisual Media, and 51 from the Faculty of Law.
- The careful selection of these three faculties at the outset was based on the assumption that students from different fields of study would present varying levels of knowledge, perception and interest in European institutions and politics. The survey results confirmed this assumption, with significant differences observed based on the faculty of study. Notably, respondents from the Faculty of Law stand out in term of their distinct levels of knowledge, perception and interest in European matters.

In summary, the project team's initial predictions and considerations were accurate, resulting in a complete and representative sample. The team's strategies and contingency plans successfully addressed the common challenge of low response rates in online surveys, ensuring a comprehensive survey implementation that effectively fulfilled the project's objective.

Specific Objective 2. To design a high-quality informative material on the relevance of the EP and the EE24 for young European citizens

The specific objective 2 was supposed to build upon survey results and foster collaboration with non-partisan civil society organisations and specialised mass-media actors in the field of European affairs. However, due to delayed approval and the European Parliament's sign-off process, adjustments were necessary. Notably, the informative dossier was completed at the beginning of March 2024—a critical timing for subsequent project activities.

To create the dossier, we subcontracted *Alternativas económicas*, an apolitical expert magazine known for its rigorous standards and commitment to independence from political influence. The magazine's team included European experts such as Andreu Missé (former EU correspondent for *El País*) and Ariadna Trillas (former EU correspondent for *Actualidad Económica*).

Additionally, we collaborated with two distinguished experts:

- Josep María Lloveras, an active partner of *Alternativas económicas* and a member of CIDOB (Barcelona Center for International Affairs). Lloveras holds a PhD in Monetary and Banking Economics from the University of Paris-1. His extensive experience includes an EU Fellowship at the European University Institute in Florence, as well as technical and managerial roles in the European Commission, particularly in enlargement policies for central and eastern European countries.
- Carme Colomina, a senior researcher specializing in the European Union, disinformation, and global politics at CIDOB. Colomina is also an associate professor at the College of Europe in Bruges, Belgium, and brings valuable insights from her extensive experience as a correspondent in Brussels.

The dossier featured the following articles:

- “Decisive Elections for the Rights of Europeans” by Andreu Missé
- “Who Does What in the European Institutions” by Mariana Vilnitzky
- “Against Disinformation: Regulation” by Carme Colomina

The dossier not only explained the functioning and role of the EP but also emphasized the importance of participating in the EE24 for younger generations. During subsequent project activities, lively debates ensued about European politics' impact on young people's daily lives and the crucial role of the Together.eu community in this context.

Specific Objective 3. To present and disseminate the content of the informative dossier

To achieve specific objective 3, several impactful activities were successfully carried out:

- **Open Event at the University of Barcelona (UB).** An open conference was held at Campus Mundet, primarily targeting UB students from the Faculty of Education. Journalists Andreu Missé (former deputy director of *El País*) and Ariadna Trillas (former correspondent in Brussels) presented the informative dossier. Professor Mihaela Vancea, the project leader, provided an overview of the entire project, upcoming activities, and details about the student communication contest and campaign. Although senior researchers Carme Colomina and Josep M. Lloveras were invited, travel constraints prevented their attendance.
- **Magazine distribution in targeted UB Faculties.** Students attending the conference received a printed version of the magazine during the Open Event. Dissemination of the dossier extended to the other two faculties—Faculty of Information and Audiovisual Media and Faculty of Law— during seminars and through additional institutional

channels. Mihaela Vancea's explanation during the open event further contextualized the project and engaged the audience to consult the dossier.

- **Advertisement and outreach.** The Open Event was widely promoted through various UB and faculty channels, including the UB communication office, dean's office, faculty secretary, UB app, website, and social media. This strategic communication ensured effective reach to the targeted audience.
- **Educational seminars.** Three seminars emphasizing the importance of voting in European elections were organized across the three targeted faculties. Speakers included Andreu Missé, Ariadna Trillas, and faculty professors Mihaela Vancea, Daniel Cetrà, and Priscila Álvarez.

Collectively, these activities contributed to the successful presentation, debate, and dissemination of the informative dossier.

Specific Objective 4. To engage UB students as active agents of change by designing and implementing an EE24 communication campaign.

Under the specific objective 4, we achieved two key aims:

- **Engagement of UB students:** we successfully involved a diverse group of UB students in the project, empowering them as active agents of change through the design and implementation of the EE24 communication campaign.
- **Youth Mobilization:** we increased awareness and mobilization among young voters about the importance of participating in the European elections.

The specific objective 4 encompassed various actions, all of which were **successfully accomplished**:

1. **Competition and selection:** we initiated a communication campaign competition that attracted submissions from students across various faculties. After careful evaluation based on criteria such as creativity, relevance, and potential impact of the proposal, we selected 10 winners. Unfortunately, due to unforeseen circumstances, two winners withdrew, leaving us with a final team of eight students.
2. **Campaign design:** the selected students collaborated closely with the UB Faculty of Education and the Communication and Audiovisual Services Unit to design the ActiveYouth_EE24 communication campaign. This campaign was tailored to students' interests, incorporating innovative and creative approaches.
3. **Campaign implementation:** the communication campaign was implemented across multiple online and offline channels, including social media, media collaborations, and community engagement initiatives. This multi-faceted approach enabled us to effectively reach a wide-ranging audience, both within and beyond the university.

Only one action contemplated by this objective was only partially achieved. We initially targeted 10 students for the communication campaign but proceeded with 8 due to withdrawals. We had to adjust the roles and responsibilities of the eight participants to ensure effective communication campaign execution.

Specific Objective 5. To assure the sustainability of the project through dissemination and communication activities and follow-up actions.

Under the specific objective 5, we achieved the following key aims:

- We created various **communication materials**, including:
 - Project logo and slogan
 - Internet information page
 - Over 400 social media posts (tweets, stories, reels and videos)

- 1 media call and 7 press releases
 - Posters and online graphic for the open event and seminars
 - Survey results and communication campaign plan presentations (PPT) (See Annex 1 and Annex 2)
 - Specific campaign materials (e.g. posters, stickers, t-shirts, big canvas) (See Annex 3 pages 4-12)
 - 10 posts on the together.eu platform
- We used various **communication channels** to disseminate the project and its activities:
- Internet websites (project page on Alternativas Económicas website, Universitat de Barcelona, Together.eu)
 - Social networks (X, Instagram, TikTok, LinkedIn)
 - Specific online tools for media outreach
 - University of Barcelona newsletters and student app
 - Physical events (open event and seminars at Universitat de Barcelona, press conference recreation at Universitat Pompeu Fabra, press conference for survey results communication at *Col·legi de Periodistes*, student campaign closing activity at the social space "Mescladís")
 - WhatsApp and email (project "friends list" and personal distribution lists of team members)
- The **dossier** was **disseminated** through different offline and online channels and promoted as teaching material in universities and other educational institutions as follows:
- Integrated content in the monthly magazine *Alternativas Económicas* (March 2024), and free-access content of its online version through the project page.
 - Promoted as a teaching material particularly at Universitat de Barcelona and Universitat Pompeu Fabra, but also at other universities and institutions thanks to *Alternativas Económicas*'s collaboration agreements (for further information about the Dossier dissemination, please see section b).
- The **seminar** content underwent meticulous **systematisation**, rendering it suitable for use in various educational contexts focused on youth political participation. One key element integral to the seminar format is the **role-playing methodology** (see section b).
- The **broadcast audiovisual content** created during the project and disseminated through social networks was **securely stored** on the project accounts for future reference. Two key activities were broadcasted, and their content stored:
- The Open Event, introducing the informative Dossier.
 - An additional event aimed at presenting survey results and the communication campaign to the media: the press conference at the *Col·legi de Periodistes de Catalunya*.
- These contents were stored and are now accessible for further consultation via [GREDI's Youtube channel](#) (GREDI is the UB's Intercultural Education Research Group, represented here by the project leader Mihaela Vancea), chosen for its suitability for long-term preservation.
- The students leading the **EE24 communication campaign** designed a **robust plan** that ensured consistent content creation and dissemination throughout the campaign. Remarkably, the results exceeded all expectations. This achievement was driven by the students' dedication, motivation, and hard work, along with guidance from Social Communication Professor at UB Anna Aroca, and support from the project team (for further information please see Annex 3).

To address the few limitations in achieving the specific objectives and ensure project sustainability, the following points can be noted:

- While the project's social media accounts are currently undergoing restructuring to emphasise informative content about European politics, the specific EE24 campaign content remains accessible here:

- [Instagram](#)
- [Twitter](#)
- [TikTok](#)

- Looking ahead, the UB research team aims to design and secure funding for a longitudinal survey study on students' knowledge and perceptions related to European institutions and politics.

b) Work performed and achievements, results and impacts

Please provide the detailed list of offline and online activities (indicating the type of activity, physical location (if offline) or channel(s) (if online), the timeline - date or period, the description of each activity). Please provide the number of people reached both directly and indirectly according to the target and estimation made in the table of key indicators and the method used to calculate (you may add relevant supporting documents) and complete the form provided by the European Parliament with the actual figures:

- 5a. for civil society actions, or
- 5b. for changemakers.

Explain how the planned activities and deliverables have served the objectives of the action and the synergy between them. Please underline any innovative approach.

In terms of work performed and achievements, results and impacts we outline below the main project activities, their alignment with objectives' fulfilment and the innovative approaches used.

ACTIVEYOUTH_EE24 SURVEY

General survey and sample information

This report is based on data gathered on June 4th, 2024, from the Active Youth_EE24 Survey, which was online from April 10th, 2024. The survey followed the methodology of Eurobarometer reports created by the European Union. The total sample consisted of 349 responses from different universities in Catalonia. Among these, 279 responses were from students at Universitat de Barcelona (UB). Notably, 233 of these UB responses came from the Faculties of Education, Information and Audiovisual Media, and Law, significantly exceeding the initial target of 150 responses from these three faculties. The survey was initially launched on April 10th, 2024, and remained online until May 28th, 2024.

In the following sections, we provide a brief summary of the general survey information (349 responses). We then present the more focused results of the three UB faculties sample (233 responses).

In terms of the general survey information, we rely on the **sociodemographic characteristics** section, explaining the sample distribution by different descriptive variables (original and recodified): language, gender, age, country of nationality, university, area of study, year of study (recodified into level of study), employment status, scholarship, and political beliefs (recodified into political ideology).

- **Language:** the survey was available in three language options: *Catalan* (208 responses), *Spanish* (138 responses), and *English* (3 responses) out of a total of 349.

- **Gender:** regarding gender distribution, there was a significant imbalance. Of the 349 responses, 221 identified as *female* (63,32%), 117 as *male* (33,81%), 3 as *non-binary* (0,86%), and 7 *preferred not to say* (2,01%).

- **Age:** the age distribution was also skewed. Predictably, considering the university context of the survey, 307 responses (87,97%) came from individuals aged *18 to 24*.

- **Country:** regarding country of nationality, 324 out of 349 respondents (92,84%) chose *Spain* as their country of nationality.

- **University:** while the majority of responses (79,94%) came from *Universitat de Barcelona*, the survey successfully gathered responses from 12 different Catalan universities.

Figure 1: University of each of the 349 respondents

- **Area of study:** the sample disproportionately represented students from the *Social Sciences and Law* area, 273 out of the 349 responses (78,22%).

- **Year of study:** this descriptive variable comprised two components. The original variable extracted directly from the survey indicates the specific academic course of respondents. Among these, *first-year* students constituted the majority of 55,59% (194 out of 349). The second variable results from recoding the first one into three levels: first-second, third-fourth, and Master and others. Notably, the *first-second* level still represented 64,18% of the total sample (224 out of 349), while the other two levels balanced at 20,63% (72 out of 349) and 14,61% (51 out of 349), respectively.

Figure 2: Year of studies for each of the 349 respondents

- **Employment status:** during the academic year, respondents' employment status showed a certain equilibrium between those *not working* (52,1%) and those *working part-time* (40,7%), whilst only 25 out of 349 (7,16%) were *working full-time*.

- **Scholarship:** when assessing scholarship support for their studies, 240 out of 349 (68,77%) students had *no scholarship*, while only 109 out of 349 (31,23%) held one.

- **Political beliefs:** respondents self-placed on a scale from 0 (far left) to 10 (far right). Nearly half of them, 45.55% (159 out of 349), positioned themselves at positions 2 or 3. When recoded into 'left' (0-4) and 'right' (5-10), the results were as follows: a significant majority of 74,21% (259 out of 349) identified with the left, while a minority of 25,21% (88 out of 349) aligned with the right.

Figure 3: Self-placed political beliefs of each of the 349 respondents

UB faculties sample information

Based on the figure below, it is evident that the three faculties specified earlier have contributed the most responses among all faculties at Universitat de Barcelona (UB). Consequently, this report conducts a detailed descriptive and explanatory analysis using the sample of 233 responses from the three targeted faculties: *Faculty of Education*, *Faculty of Information and Audiovisual Media*, and *Faculty of Law*.

Figure 4: Faculty of the UB each of the 279 UB respondents is enrolled in

We examined the new sample of 233 responses from the three aforementioned faculties. By analysing descriptive variables, we gained a general understanding of the sample and identified

possible imbalances relevant for the subsequent explanatory analysis. The sociodemographic characteristics explored were the following (original and recodified): gender, age, country of nationality, area of studies, year of studies (recodified into 'level of studies'), employment status, scholarship, and political beliefs (recodified into 'political ideology').

Descriptive analysis

As a preamble to these descriptive analysis, it is important to reiterate that all 233 responses come from Universitat de Barcelona (UB), specifically, from the three targeted faculties: Faculty of Education, Faculty of Information and Audiovisual Media, and Faculty of Law. The sample distribution across these faculties is relatively balanced, although the Faculty of Education slightly stands out with 104 out of the total 233 responses (44,64%).

Figure 5: Distribution of the 233 respondents within the three target UB faculties

- **Gender.** Gender distribution among respondents reveals a significant imbalance: 164 out of 233 responses came from *female* (70,39%), 62 responses from *male* (26,61%), only 1 response from *non-binary* (0,43%), and 6 responses *preferred not to say* (2,58%).

Figure 6: Gender of the 233 respondents

- **Age.** With respect to the age distribution, the sample is also unbalanced as 219 out of 233 responses (93,99%) came from people aged between 18 and 24 years old.

- **Country.** The same situation emerges for respondents' country *of nationality*. Approximately 94,42% of respondents (220 out of 233) identified as Spanish nationals.

- **Area of study.** Given the nature of the three targeted faculties, the sample came exclusively from the *Social Sciences and Law* area of study.

- **Level of study.** The original variable measured the exact academic course in which respondents were enrolled. The recodified variable was created by grouping the original courses into three categories: *first-second level*, *third-fourth level*, *Master and others*. The first category accounted for a substantial 80,26% of the total sample (187 out of 233); approximately 15,02% of respondents fell into the second category (35 out of 233); and the third category comprised only 4,29% of the total sample (10 out of 233). Given the project's limitations and survey distribution methods, it is essential to acknowledge the dominance of the *first-second* level course.

Figure 7: Level of studies of the 233 respondents

- **Employment status.** The employment status of respondents during the academic year shows a certain balance between 53,22% *not working* (124 of 233) and 39,06% *working part-time* (91 of 233), while expectedly only 7,73% were *working full-time* (18 of 233).

Figure 8: Employment status of the 233 respondents

- **Scholarship.** The scholarship variable could be interpreted as a social class indicator variable, though as we see in the following explicative analysis, it does not have a significant impact. A majority of students, 63,95% (149 out of 233), had no scholarship, while 36,05% held one (84 out of 233).

Scholarship supporting your studies

Figure 9: Ownership of a scholarship by the 233 respondents

- **Political ideology.** The original variable extracted directly from the survey, represented respondents' self-placement on a scale from 0 (far left) to 10 (far-right) based on their political beliefs. The recodified variable was created by grouping the original responses into two categories: *left* (from 0 to 4) and *right* (from 5 to 10). A significant majority of respondents, 75,11% (175 out of 233) fell into the *left* category, while only 24,46% (57 out of 233) identified with the *right*-leaning positions.

Figure 10: Self-placed political beliefs of the 233

General self-assigned political ideology

Figure 11: Political ideology of the 233 respondents

Explicative analysis based on the five survey blocks

After presenting the descriptive analysis of our data, we now conduct an explanatory analysis on the same sample (233 student responses from the three UB faculties). This analysis is divided into five distinct sections, each centered around a key variable or survey question. The five blocks are inspired by the survey's thematic sections: I. Knowledge about European institutions and elections, II. Access to information and media about European politics, III. Perception of the European Parliament and European elections, and IV. Participation in European politics.

The five blocks are as follows: 1. Participation; 2. Information; 3. Interest; 4. Knowledge (4.1. Knowledge European election results, and 4.2. Knowledge European Parliament's main function); 5. Opinion/Assessment.

Each section begins with a general description, typically presented through a contingency table, of the key variable associated with that block. We then cross-tabulate this variable with different socio-demographic characteristics, previously discussed in the descriptive analysis. However, we excluded variables where one group category represents more than 90% of the sample (specifically *age*, *country of nationality*, and *area of studies*). For each key variable, we performed crosstabulations with the following socio-demographic variables: faculty, gender, employment status, level of study, scholarship, political ideology (left or right).

The scholarship variable did not exhibit significant explanatory potential in any of the blocks. Consequently, we present only statistically significant associations by faculty, gender, employment status, level of study, and political ideology.

Block 1. Participation

In order to analyse the participation of respondents in European politics we focused on their opinions regarding European parliament elections: *What is your opinion on European Parliament elections?*

"I don't have a defined opinion" is the most common response (35.19%), indicating indecisiveness or neutrality. Over 55% of respondents exhibit a passive attitude toward EP elections, either by not participating or lacking a clear opinion about their importance. Encouragingly, more than 26% of respondents (62 out of 233) consider Elections important and tend to actively participate in them.

Table 1.1. Individual frequency distribution of Participation

What is your opinion on European Parliament elections?				
Xi	ni	fi	Ni	Fi
Important and I participate.	62	26,61%	62	26,61%
Important, but I don't always participate.	38	16,31%	100	42,92%
I don't give them much importance and I don't participate.	47	20,17%	147	63,09%
I don't have a defined opinion.	82	35,19%	229	98,28%
-	4	1,72%	233	100,00%
TOTAL	233	100,00%	233	100,00%

Opinion and participation in elections to the European Parliament

Figure 1.1: Participation in European elections of the 233 respondents

Participation by faculty

Table 1.2 examines the relationship between respondents' faculty and their participation opinions regarding EP elections.

The dominant response "I don't have a defined opinion" is prevalent among students from the Faculty of Education (40,4%) and the Faculty of Information and Audiovisual Media (42,3%). In contrast, the majority of respondents from the Faculty of Law responded "Important and I participate" (54,9%). The cross-tabulation results are significant at the 1% level, indicating statistically significant associations (Table 1.3).

While students from the Faculty of Education constitute a substantial majority across other response categories (as expected due to their overrepresentation in the sample), this balance shifts in the "Important and I participate" response. Students from the Faculty of Law break this imbalance, representing a dominant 45,2% of the total consistently active participants in EP elections.

Hence, students from the Faculty of Law exhibit higher active participation in EP elections compared to their counterparts in the other two faculties. Additionally, they express much less indecisiveness (Figure 1.2).

Table 1.2. Participation in European elections by target UB faculty

In which faculty? * What is your opinion on European Parliament elections? Crosstabulation

		What is your opinion on European Parliament elections?						
			Important and I participate.	Important, but I don't always participate.	I don't give them much importance and I don't participate.	I don't have a defined opinion.	Total	
In which faculty?	Faculty of Education	Count	13	23	23	42	3	104
		% within In which faculty?	12,5%	22,1%	22,1%	40,4%	2,9%	100,0%
		% within What is your opinion on European Parliament elections?	21,0%	60,5%	48,9%	51,2%	75,0%	44,6%
		% of Total	5,6%	9,9%	9,9%	18,0%	1,3%	44,6%
	Faculty of Information and Audiovisual Media	Count	21	7	17	33	0	78
		% within In which faculty?	26,9%	9,0%	21,8%	42,3%	0,0%	100,0%
		% within What is your opinion on European Parliament elections?	33,9%	18,4%	36,2%	40,2%	0,0%	33,5%
		% of Total	9,0%	3,0%	7,3%	14,2%	0,0%	33,5%
	Faculty of Law	Count	28	8	7	7	1	51
		% within In which faculty?	54,9%	15,7%	13,7%	13,7%	2,0%	100,0%
		% within What is your opinion on European Parliament elections?	45,2%	21,1%	14,9%	8,5%	25,0%	21,9%
		% of Total	12,0%	3,4%	3,0%	3,0%	0,4%	21,9%
Total	Count	62	38	47	82	4	233	
	% within In which faculty?	26,6%	16,3%	20,2%	35,2%	1,7%	100,0%	
	% within What is your opinion on European Parliament elections?	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	
	% of Total	26,6%	16,3%	20,2%	35,2%	1,7%	100,0%	

Table 1.3. Significance tests for participation by target UB faculty

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	39,987 ^a	8	<,001
Likelihood Ratio	41,812	8	<,001
N of Valid Cases	233		

a. 3 cells (20,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is ,88.

Figure 1.2: Participation in European elections by target UB faculty

Participation by employment status

Table 1.4 examines how respondents' employment status relates to their participation opinions regarding EP elections.

The dominant response "I don't have a defined opinion" is significantly prevalent among students who do not work (44%) and, to a lesser extent, among part-time workers (29%). Conversely, the majority of respondents who work full-time answered "Important and I participate" (38,9%). The

cross-tabulation results are significant at the 1% level, indicating statistically significant associations (Table 1.5).

Students who work part-time constitute a substantial majority of those who participate in some way —either actively (48,4% are part-time workers) or occasionally (73,7% are part-time workers). In contrast, students who do not work during the academic year represent the majority of those who express indecisiveness (48,4% of the total indecisive responses).

Students who do not work during the academic year tend to exhibit proportionately less participative behavior and a more indecisive attitude towards EP elections compared to those who work while studying (Figure 1.3). Although the difference is not highly significant, it highlights the impact of employment status on political engagement.

Table 1.4. Participation in European elections by employment status

Do you work during the academic year while studying? * What is your opinion on European Parliament elections? Crosstabulation

			What is your opinion on European Parliament elections?				Total	
			Important and I participate.	Important, but I don't always participate.	I don't give them much importance and I don't participate.	I don't have a defined opinion.		
Do you work during the academic year while studying?	Yes, full-time	Count	7	3	2	6	0	18
		% within Do you work during the academic year while studying?	38,9%	16,7%	11,1%	33,3%	0,0%	100,0%
		% within What is your opinion on European Parliament elections?	11,3%	7,9%	4,3%	7,3%	0,0%	7,7%
		% of Total	3,0%	1,3%	0,9%	2,6%	0,0%	7,7%
	Yes, part-time	Count	30	28	27	36	3	124
		% within Do you work during the academic year while studying?	24,2%	22,6%	21,8%	29,0%	2,4%	100,0%
		% within What is your opinion on European Parliament elections?	48,4%	73,7%	57,4%	43,9%	75,0%	53,2%
		% of Total	12,9%	12,0%	11,6%	15,5%	1,3%	53,2%
	No	Count	25	7	18	40	1	91
		% within Do you work during the academic year while studying?	27,5%	7,7%	19,8%	44,0%	1,1%	100,0%
		% within What is your opinion on European Parliament elections?	40,3%	18,4%	38,3%	48,8%	25,0%	39,1%
		% of Total	10,7%	3,0%	7,7%	17,2%	0,4%	39,1%
Total	Count	62	38	47	82	4	233	
	% within Do you work during the academic year while studying?	26,6%	16,3%	20,2%	35,2%	1,7%	100,0%	
	% within What is your opinion on European Parliament elections?	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	
	% of Total	26,6%	16,3%	20,2%	35,2%	1,7%	100,0%	

Table 1.5. Significance tests for participation by employment status

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	13,558 ^a	8	,094
Likelihood Ratio	14,511	8	,069
N of Valid Cases	233		

a. 6 cells (40,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is ,31.

Figure 1.3: Participation in European elections by employment status

Participation by level of study

In the cross tabulation below (Table 1.6), significant at 5% significance level (Table 1.7), we can compare the responses to the question on participation regarding the level of studies of the respondent.

The indecisive response “I don’t have a defined opinion” is dominant in the level First-Second (39,6%) but not in the other two. Contrarily, the majority of respondents in level Third-Fourth (42,9%) and in level Master and others (70%) responded “Important and I participate”.

Hence, while the students from the level First-Second are an enormous majority of more than 80% in all the other answers, something predictable given their disproportionate overrepresentation in the 233 sample, in the case of the response “Important and I participate” they represent only the 62,9%, resulting the sample imbalance with the other two levels somewhat disguised in this answer.

Therefore, we can conclude that students from more mature level of studies are proportionately much more actively participative in EP elections than those in the First-Second level, and also less indecisive (Figure 1.4).

Table 1.6. Participation in European elections by level of studies

Level of studies currently enrolled in * What is your opinion on European Parliament elections? Crosstabulation

		What is your opinion on European Parliament elections?						
			Important and I participate.	Important, but I don't always participate.	I don't give them much importance and I don't participate.	I don't have a defined opinion.	Total	
Level of studies currently enrolled in	First-Second	Count	39	31	39	74	4	187
		% within Level of studies currently enrolled in	20,9%	16,6%	20,9%	39,6%	2,1%	100,0%
		% within What is your opinion on European Parliament elections?	62,9%	81,6%	83,0%	90,2%	100,0%	80,3%
	Third-Fourth	% of Total	16,7%	13,3%	16,7%	31,8%	1,7%	80,3%
		Count	15	5	7	8	0	35
		% within Level of studies currently enrolled in	42,9%	14,3%	20,0%	22,9%	0,0%	100,0%
	Master and others	% within What is your opinion on European Parliament elections?	24,2%	13,2%	14,9%	9,8%	0,0%	15,0%
		% of Total	6,4%	2,1%	3,0%	3,4%	0,0%	15,0%
		Count	7	2	1	0	0	10
		% within Level of studies currently enrolled in	70,0%	20,0%	10,0%	0,0%	0,0%	100,0%
		% within What is your opinion on European Parliament elections?	11,3%	5,3%	2,1%	0,0%	0,0%	4,3%
		% of Total	3,0%	0,9%	0,4%	0,0%	0,0%	4,3%
	Count	1	0	0	0	0	1	
	% within Level of studies currently enrolled in	100,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	100,0%	
	% within What is your opinion on European Parliament elections?	1,6%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,4%	
	% of Total	0,4%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,4%	
	Count	62	38	47	82	4	233	
	% within Level of studies currently enrolled in	26,6%	16,3%	20,2%	35,2%	1,7%	100,0%	
Total	% within What is your opinion on European Parliament elections?	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	
	% of Total	26,6%	16,3%	20,2%	35,2%	1,7%	100,0%	

Table 1.7. Significance tests for participation by level of studies

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	23,387 ^a	12	,025
Likelihood Ratio	25,276	12	,014
N of Valid Cases	233		

a. 12 cells (60,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is ,02.

Figure 1.4: Participation in European elections by level of studies

To assess students' awareness of European politics, we selected a key question that reflects their frequency of staying informed: *How often do you follow news about European politics?*

The most common response is “occasionally”, followed by “never”. These two categories account for a significant 68,67% of respondents. Only 30,47% of respondents follow news about European politics at least once a month. A mere 3,43% of participants stay informed on a daily basis.

Table 2.1. Individual frequency distribution of Information

How often do you follow news about European politics?				
Xi	ni	fi	Ni	Fi
Daily	8	3,43%	8	3,43%
Weekly	32	13,73%	40	17,17%
Monthly	31	13,30%	71	30,47%
Occasionally	111	47,64%	182	78,11%
Never	49	21,03%	231	99,14%
-	2	0,86%	233	100,00%
TOTAL	233	100,00%	233	100,00%

Frequency of information about European politics

Figure 2.1: Frequency of information about European politics of the 233 respondents

Information by faculty

In the cross tabulation below (Table 2.2), which is significant at 1% level (Table 2.3), we compare responses related to the respondents' faculties.

The dominant response “occasionally” prevails in the Faculty of Education (57,7%) and the Faculty of Information and Audiovisual Media (50%). However, a significant percentage of respondents from the Faculty of Law report following news “weekly” (37,3%).

We also find that students from the Faculty of Education maintain their substantial sample majority (over 50%) among the less informed —those who follow news “occasionally” or “never”.

Meanwhile, the Faculty of Information and Audiovisual Media has the highest proportion (45,2%) of students who follow news “monthly”. In contrast, students from the Faculty of Law significantly disrupt the sample imbalance, representing around 60% of respondents, in those who fail into the most informed categories: those who follow European politics news “weekly” or “daily”.

In conclusion, students from the Faculty of Law exhibit greater awareness of European politics compared to their counterparts in the other two faculties, while those from the Faculty of Education are the least informed (Figure 2.2).

Table 2.2. Information about European politics by target UB faculty

In which faculty? * How often do you follow news about European politics? Crosstabulation

			How often do you follow news about European politics?					Total	
			Daily	Weekly	Monthly	Occasionally	Never		
In which faculty?	Faculty of Education	Count	2	8	6	60	26	2	104
		% within In which faculty?	1,9%	7,7%	5,8%	57,7%	25,0%	1,9%	100,0%
		% within How often do you follow news about European politics?	25,0%	25,0%	19,4%	54,1%	53,1%	100,0%	44,6%
		% of Total	0,9%	3,4%	2,6%	25,8%	11,2%	0,9%	44,6%
	Faculty of Information and Audiovisual Media	Count	1	5	14	39	19	0	78
		% within In which faculty?	1,3%	6,4%	17,9%	50,0%	24,4%	0,0%	100,0%
		% within How often do you follow news about European politics?	12,5%	15,6%	45,2%	35,1%	38,8%	0,0%	33,5%
		% of Total	0,4%	2,1%	6,0%	16,7%	8,2%	0,0%	33,5%
	Faculty of Law	Count	5	19	11	12	4	0	51
		% within In which faculty?	9,8%	37,3%	21,6%	23,5%	7,8%	0,0%	100,0%
		% within How often do you follow news about European politics?	62,5%	59,4%	35,5%	10,8%	8,2%	0,0%	21,9%
		% of Total	2,1%	8,2%	4,7%	5,2%	1,7%	0,0%	21,9%
Total	Count	8	32	31	111	49	2	233	
	% within In which faculty?	3,4%	13,7%	13,3%	47,6%	21,0%	0,9%	100,0%	
	% within How often do you follow news about European politics?	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	
	% of Total	3,4%	13,7%	13,3%	47,6%	21,0%	0,9%	100,0%	

Table 2.3. Significance tests for information by target UB faculty

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	58,854 ^a	10	<,001
Likelihood Ratio	55,945	10	<,001
N of Valid Cases	233		

a. 6 cells (33,3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is ,44.

Figure 2.2: Information about European politics by target UB faculty

Information by level of study

In the cross-tabulation below (Table 2.4), which is significant at the 5% level (Table 2.5), we compare responses related to the respondents’ level of studies.

For the first-second level students, the dominant response is “occasionally”, accounting for 48,7%. For third-fourth level students, as in the case of first-second level students, “occasionally” is the dominant response, with 48,6%. However, in Master and other superior levels, the distribution is shared between “occasionally” and “weekly”, both at 30%. Note that the sample size for students in this category is relatively small.

Considering the imbalance caused by the overrepresentation of first-second level students in the 233-sample (over 80%), it is noticeable that students from the first-second level represent only 65,6% of those who follow news ”weekly”. And only 37,5% of those following news ”daily” are first-second level students, a percentage matched by students from the third-fourth level.

In summary, students at more advanced levels of study are proportionately more frequently informed about European politics than those in the first-second level. Additionally, the gap between the most and least informed groups is narrower among mature-level students (Figure 2.3).

Table 2.4. Information about European politics by level of studies

Level of studies currently enrolled in * How often do you follow news about European politics? Crosstabulation

			How often do you follow news about European politics?					Total	
			Daily	Weekly	Monthly	Occasionally	Never		
Level of studies currently enrolled in	First-Second	Count	3	21	26	91	44	2	187
		% within Level of studies currently enrolled in	1,6%	11,2%	13,9%	48,7%	23,5%	1,1%	100,0%
		% within How often do you follow news about European politics?	37,5%	65,6%	83,9%	82,0%	89,8%	100,0%	80,3%
		% of Total	1,3%	9,0%	11,2%	39,1%	18,9%	0,9%	80,3%
	Third-Fourth	Count	3	8	2	17	5	0	35
		% within Level of studies currently enrolled in	8,6%	22,9%	5,7%	48,6%	14,3%	0,0%	100,0%
		% within How often do you follow news about European politics?	37,5%	25,0%	6,5%	15,3%	10,2%	0,0%	15,0%
		% of Total	1,3%	3,4%	0,9%	7,3%	2,1%	0,0%	15,0%
	Master and others	Count	2	3	2	3	0	0	10
		% within Level of studies currently enrolled in	20,0%	30,0%	20,0%	30,0%	0,0%	0,0%	100,0%
		% within How often do you follow news about European politics?	25,0%	9,4%	6,5%	2,7%	0,0%	0,0%	4,3%
		% of Total	0,9%	1,3%	0,9%	1,3%	0,0%	0,0%	4,3%
	Count	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	
	% within Level of studies currently enrolled in	0,0%	0,0%	100,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	100,0%	
	% within How often do you follow news about European politics?	0,0%	0,0%	3,2%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,4%	
	% of Total	0,0%	0,0%	0,4%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,4%	
Total	Count	8	32	31	111	49	2	233	
	% within Level of studies currently enrolled in	3,4%	13,7%	13,3%	47,6%	21,0%	0,9%	100,0%	
	% within How often do you follow news about European politics?	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	
	% of Total	3,4%	13,7%	13,3%	47,6%	21,0%	0,9%	100,0%	

Table 2.5. Significance tests for information by level of studies

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	30,427 ^a	15	,010
Likelihood Ratio	25,579	15	,043
N of Valid Cases	233		

a. 17 cells (70,8%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is ,01.

Frequency of information about European politics depending on Level of studies

Figure 2.3: Information about European politics by level of studies

Information by political ideology

In the cross-tabulation below (Table 2.6), which is significant at the 1% level (Table 2.7), we compare responses related to the respondents' political ideologies.

In the case of the left ideology, the dominant response is "occasionally", accounting for 50,3%. However, this dominance is less pronounced among students with a right-leaning ideology 40,4%.

Solely breaking the sample imbalance (over 70% identify as left), students who follow news "daily" about European politics are primarily from the right-leaning group (62,5%).

In summary, students who identify with right-leaning political beliefs tend to be more frequently informed on a daily basis, whereas those in the left are proportionately more "occasionally" informed (Figure 2.4).

Table 2.6. Information about European politics by political ideology

Political ideology Left (0,1,2,3,4) or Right (5,6,7,8,9,10) according to self-placement in a scale of 0(far left) to 10(far right) *
How often do you follow news about European politics? Crosstabulation

		How often do you follow news about European politics?					Total			
		Daily	Weekly	Monthly	Occasionally	Never				
Political ideology Left (0,1,2,3,4) or Right (5,6,7,8,9,10) according to self-placement in a scale of 0(far left) to 10(far right)	Left	Count	2	25	24	88	35	1	175	
		% within Political ideology Left (0,1,2,3,4) or Right (5,6,7,8,9,10) according to self-placement in a scale of 0(far left) to 10(far right)	1,1%	14,3%	13,7%	50,3%	20,0%	0,6%	100,0%	
		% within How often do you follow news about European politics?	25,0%	78,1%	77,4%	79,3%	71,4%	50,0%	75,1%	
		% of Total	0,9%	10,7%	10,3%	37,8%	15,0%	0,4%	75,1%	
		Right	Count	5	7	7	23	14	1	57
			% within Political ideology Left (0,1,2,3,4) or Right (5,6,7,8,9,10) according to self-placement in a scale of 0(far left) to 10(far right)	8,8%	12,3%	12,3%	40,4%	24,6%	1,8%	100,0%
	% within How often do you follow news about European politics?		62,5%	21,9%	22,6%	20,7%	28,6%	50,0%	24,5%	
	% of Total		2,1%	3,0%	3,0%	9,9%	6,0%	0,4%	24,5%	
	Total		Count	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
			% within Political ideology Left (0,1,2,3,4) or Right (5,6,7,8,9,10) according to self-placement in a scale of 0(far left) to 10(far right)	100,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	100,0%
		% within How often do you follow news about European politics?	12,5%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,4%	
		% of Total	0,4%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,4%	
Count		8	32	31	111	49	2	233		
% within Political ideology Left (0,1,2,3,4) or Right (5,6,7,8,9,10) according to self-placement in a scale of 0(far left) to 10(far right)		3,4%	13,7%	13,3%	47,6%	21,0%	0,9%	100,0%		
% within How often do you follow news about European politics?	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%			
% of Total	3,4%	13,7%	13,3%	47,6%	21,0%	0,9%	100,0%			

Table 2.7. Significance tests for information by political ideology

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	37,744 ^a	10	<,001
Likelihood Ratio	15,784	10	,106
N of Valid Cases	233		

a. 9 cells (50,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is ,01.

Figure 2.4: Information about European politics by political ideology

Block 3. Interest

To analyse students' interest in European politics, we selected the following question as the most representative: *Are you interested in European politics?*

The data (Table 3.1, Figure 3.1) show a moderate interest, as the most common response is "Yes, I am interested, but I don't always follow it closely". Following close behind is the response "No, I am not very interested in European politics". Approximately 43% of respondents express some level of interest. About 39% indicate a lack of interest. Notably, over 55% of participants show general disinterest or an undefined level of interest in European politics.

Table 3.1. Individual frequency distribution of Interest

Are you interested in European politics?				
Xi	ni	fi	Ni	Fi
Yes, I am very interested and actively follow it.	12	5,15%	12	5,15%
Yes, I am interested, but I don't always follow it closely.	89	38,20%	101	43,35%
I have no defined opinion on European politics.	38	16,31%	139	59,66%
No, I am not very interested in European politics.	74	31,76%	213	91,42%
I have no interest in European politics.	17	7,30%	230	98,71%
-	3	1,29%	233	100,00%
TOTAL	233	100,00%	233	100,00%

Figure 3.1: Interest in European politics of the 233 respondents

Interest by faculty

In the cross-tabulation below (Table 3.2), which is significant at the 1% level (Table 3.3), we compare responses related to the respondents' faculties and their interest in European politics.

For the Faculty of Information and Audiovisual Media, the dominant response is "No, I am not very interested in European politics", accounting for 38,5%. Contrarily, at the Faculty of Law, the response "Yes, I am interested, but I don't always follow it closely" prevails, representing 52,9%. Interestingly, at the Faculty of Education there is an equal distribution between the two moderate interest options: "Yes, I am interested, but I don't always follow it closely" and "No, I am not interested in European politics", both at 34,6%.

Besides, we observe that students from the Faculty of Education hold their substantial sample-majority in almost all responses with more than 40%. For students with no clearly defined interest in European politics, both the Faculty of Education and the Faculty of Information and Audiovisual Media share the same percentage of respondents (47,4% each). Nonetheless, students from the Faculty of Law significantly break the sample imbalance representing a substantial majority (91,7%) of those who respond "Yes, I am very interested and actively follow it".

In summary, students from the Faculty of Law exhibit greater interest, both moderately and actively, in European politics compared to those in the other two faculties, while the Faculty of Education remains the least defined in terms of interest (Figure 3.2).

Table 3.2. Interest in European politics by target UB faculty

In which faculty? * Are you interested in European politics? Crosstabulation

		Are you interested in European politics?					Total		
		Yes, I am very interested and actively follow it.	Yes, I am interested, but I don't always follow it closely.	I have no defined opinion on European politics.	No, I am not very interested in European politics.	I have no interest in European politics.			
In which faculty?	Faculty of Education	Count	1	36	18	36	11	2	104
		% within In which faculty?	1,0%	34,6%	17,3%	34,6%	10,6%	1,9%	100,0%
		% within Are you interested in European politics?	8,3%	40,4%	47,4%	48,6%	64,7%	66,7%	44,6%
		% of Total	0,4%	15,5%	7,7%	15,5%	4,7%	0,9%	44,6%
Faculty of Information and Audiovisual Media	Count	0	26	18	30	4	0	78	
	% within In which faculty?	0,0%	33,3%	23,1%	38,5%	5,1%	0,0%	100,0%	
	% within Are you interested in European politics?	0,0%	29,2%	47,4%	40,5%	23,5%	0,0%	33,5%	
	% of Total	0,0%	11,2%	7,7%	12,9%	1,7%	0,0%	33,5%	
Faculty of Law	Count	11	27	2	8	2	1	51	
	% within In which faculty?	21,6%	52,9%	3,9%	15,7%	3,9%	2,0%	100,0%	
	% within Are you interested in European politics?	91,7%	30,3%	5,3%	10,8%	11,8%	33,3%	21,9%	
	% of Total	4,7%	11,6%	0,9%	3,4%	0,9%	0,4%	21,9%	
Total	Count	12	89	38	74	17	3	233	
	% within In which faculty?	5,2%	38,2%	16,3%	31,8%	7,3%	1,3%	100,0%	
	% within Are you interested in European politics?	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	
	% of Total	5,2%	38,2%	16,3%	31,8%	7,3%	1,3%	100,0%	

Table 3.3. Significance tests for interest by target UB faculty

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	54,903 ^a	10	<,001
Likelihood Ratio	52,252	10	<,001
N of Valid Cases	233		

a. 6 cells (33,3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is ,66.

Figure 3.2: Interest in European politics by target UB faculty

Interest by level of study

In the cross-tabulation below (Table 3.4), which is significant at the 1% level (Table 3.5), we compare responses related to the students' levels of study and their interest in European politics.

In the case of first-second level students, the dominant response is "Yes, I am interested, but I don't always follow it closely", accounting for 38%. Similarly, in the third-fourth level, this response prevails, representing 42,9%. In the Master and other levels, the distribution is shared among three responses, with each expressing some degree of interest. Each response represents 30% of the students. Note that the sample size for students in this category is small.

Breaking the sample imbalance (over 75% dominance from the first-second level), students from the third-fourth level represent 50% of the total responses for the option "Yes, I am very interested and actively follow it", while students from the Master and other levels represent 25%, the same as the first-second level.

In summary, students at more advanced levels of study are more actively interested and proportionately more interested overall in European politics than those in first-second level. Additionally, they exhibit less undefined interest (Figure 3.3).

Table 3.4. Interest in European politics by level of studies

Level of studies currently enrolled in * Are you interested in European politics? Crosstabulation

			Are you interested in European politics?					Total	
			Yes, I am very interested and actively follow it.	Yes, I am interested, but I don't always follow it closely.	I have no defined opinion on European politics.	No, I am not very interested in European politics.	I have no interest in European politics.		
Level of studies currently enrolled in	First-Second	Count	3	71	35	62	13	3	187
		% within Level of studies currently enrolled in	1,6%	38,0%	18,7%	33,2%	7,0%	1,6%	100,0%
		% within Are you interested in European politics?	25,0%	79,8%	92,1%	83,8%	76,5%	100,0%	80,3%
		% of Total	1,3%	30,5%	15,0%	26,6%	5,6%	1,3%	80,3%
	Third-Fourth	Count	6	15	2	8	4	0	35
		% within Level of studies currently enrolled in	17,1%	42,9%	5,7%	22,9%	11,4%	0,0%	100,0%
		% within Are you interested in European politics?	50,0%	16,9%	5,3%	10,8%	23,5%	0,0%	15,0%
		% of Total	2,6%	6,4%	0,9%	3,4%	1,7%	0,0%	15,0%
	Master and others	Count	3	3	1	3	0	0	10
		% within Level of studies currently enrolled in	30,0%	30,0%	10,0%	30,0%	0,0%	0,0%	100,0%
		% within Are you interested in European politics?	25,0%	3,4%	2,6%	4,1%	0,0%	0,0%	4,3%
		% of Total	1,3%	1,3%	0,4%	1,3%	0,0%	0,0%	4,3%
		Count	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
		% within Level of studies currently enrolled in	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	100,0%	0,0%	0,0%	100,0%
		% within Are you interested in European politics?	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	1,4%	0,0%	0,0%	0,4%
% of Total		0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,4%	0,0%	0,0%	0,4%	
Total	Count	12	89	38	74	17	3	233	
	% within Level of studies currently enrolled in	5,2%	38,2%	16,3%	31,8%	7,3%	1,3%	100,0%	
	% within Are you interested in European politics?	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	
	% of Total	5,2%	38,2%	16,3%	31,8%	7,3%	1,3%	100,0%	

Table 3.5. Significance tests for interest by level of studies

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	35,475 ^a	15	,002
Likelihood Ratio	29,292	15	,015
N of Valid Cases	233		

a. 16 cells (66,7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is ,01.

Figure 3.3: Interest in European politics by level of studies

Interest by political ideology

In the cross-tabulation below (Table 3.6), which is significant at the 10% level (Table 3.7), we compare responses related to the students’ political ideologies and their interest in European politics.

The moderate response “Yes, I am interested, but I don't always follow it closely” is similarly dominant in both the left (39,4%) and the right (35,1%).

Among those who respond ”I have no interest in European politics”, the left-leaning students account for 64,7%, while the right-leaning students represent 35,3%. Notably, the sample imbalance (over 75% identified with the left) is completely overturned for the response “Yes, I am very interested and actively follow it”. Here, the majority (58,3%) comes from the right-leaning group.

In summary, students who align with right-leaning political beliefs tend to have a more active interest in European politics, while those from the left are more moderate with their interest (Figure 3.4).

Table 3.6. Interest in European politics by political ideology

Political ideology Left (0,1,2,3,4) or Right (5,6,7,8,9,10) according to self-placement in a scale of 0(far left) to 10(far right) * Are you interested in European politics? Crosstabulation

		Are you interested in European politics?					Total		
		Yes, I am very interested and actively follow it.	Yes, I am interested, but I don't always follow it closely.	I have no defined opinion on European politics.	No, I am not very interested in European politics.	I have no interest in European politics.			
Political ideology Left (0,1,2,3,4) or Right (5,6,7,8,9,10) according to self-placement in a scale of 0(far left) to 10(far right)	Left	Count	5	69	32	56	11	2	175
		% within Political ideology Left (0,1,2,3,4) or Right (5,6,7,8,9,10) according to self-placement in a scale of 0(far left) to 10(far right)	2,9%	39,4%	18,3%	32,0%	6,3%	1,1%	100,0%
		% within Are you interested in European politics?	41,7%	77,5%	84,2%	75,7%	64,7%	66,7%	75,1%
	Right	Count	7	20	5	18	6	1	57
		% within Political ideology Left (0,1,2,3,4) or Right (5,6,7,8,9,10) according to self-placement in a scale of 0(far left) to 10(far right)	12,3%	35,1%	8,8%	31,6%	10,5%	1,8%	100,0%
		% within Are you interested in European politics?	58,3%	22,5%	13,2%	24,3%	35,3%	33,3%	24,5%
	Total	Count	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
		% within Political ideology Left (0,1,2,3,4) or Right (5,6,7,8,9,10) according to self-placement in a scale of 0(far left) to 10(far right)	0,0%	0,0%	100,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	100,0%
		% within Are you interested in European politics?	0,0%	0,0%	2,6%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,4%
	Total	Count	12	89	38	74	17	3	233
% within Political ideology Left (0,1,2,3,4) or Right (5,6,7,8,9,10) according to self-placement in a scale of 0(far left) to 10(far right)		5,2%	38,2%	16,3%	31,8%	7,3%	1,3%	100,0%	
% within Are you interested in European politics?		100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	
% of Total		5,2%	38,2%	16,3%	31,8%	7,3%	1,3%	100,0%	

Table 3.7. Significance tests for interest by political ideology

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	16,353 ^a	10	,090
Likelihood Ratio	13,902	10	,178
N of Valid Cases	233		

a. 10 cells (55,6%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is ,01.

Figure 3.4: Interest in European politics by political ideology

To assess students' knowledge of EP elections, we focus on two key questions: one regarding 2024 EP election results and another concerning the main function of the EP.

4.1. Knowledge 2024 EP election results

We begin by examining students' awareness of the 2024 EP election results. The central question is: *Are you informed about the foreseeable results of the upcoming European parliamentary elections in June 2024?*

The response "No, I am not very informed about it" dominates, representing more than half of the total responses (52,79%). Remarkably, over 80% of respondents lacked clear knowledge of the foreseeable election results. Only 17,6% of participants had some understanding of what might happen in the EP elections. A mere 4,72% demonstrated good knowledge of the EP possible election outcomes.

In summary, most students lacked awareness about the upcoming EP elections (Figure 4.1.1).

Table 4.1.1. Individual frequency distribution of Knowledge about EP elections

Are you informed about the foreseeable results of the upcoming European parliamentary elections in June 2024?				
Xi	ni	fi	Ni	Fi
Yes, I am well informed about the possible results.	11	4,72%	11	4,72%
Yes, I have a general idea of what might happen.	30	12,88%	41	17,60%
No, I am not very informed about it.	123	52,79%	164	70,39%
I don't know, I haven't followed the news related to these elections.	65	27,90%	229	98,28%
-	4	1,72%	233	100,00%
TOTAL	233	100,00%	233	100,00%

Knowledge about the foreseeable results of European elections June 2024

Figure 4.1.1: Knowledge about EP elections of the 233 respondents

Knowledge EP election results by faculty

In the cross-tabulation below (Table 4.1.2), which is significant at the 1% level (Table 4.1.3), we compare responses related to students' faculties and their knowledge about the EP election results.

At the Faculty of Education, the dominant response is “No, I am not very informed about it”, accounting for 48,1%. At the Faculty of Information and Audiovisual Media, the same response “No, I am not very informed about it” prevails as well, with 64,1%.

Interestingly, in the specific response “I don’t know, I haven’t followed the news related to these elections”, students from the Faculty of Education represent 58,5%. Breaking the sample imbalance, students from the Faculty of Law represent 50% of those who respond “yes, I have a general idea of what might happen”, and a substantial majority (72,7%) of those who answer “Yes, I am well informed about the possible results”.

In summary, students from the Faculty of Law demonstrate significantly greater knowledge and awareness of the foreseeable EP election results compared to their counterparts in other faculties (Figure 4.1.2).

Table 4.1.2. Knowledge about EP elections by target UB faculty

In which faculty? * Are you informed about the foreseeable results of the upcoming European parliamentary elections in June 2024?
Crosstabulation

		Are you informed about the foreseeable results of the upcoming European parliamentary elections in June 2024?					Total		
		Yes, I am well informed about the possible results.	Yes, I have a general idea of what might happen.	No, I am not very informed about it.	I don't know, I haven't followed the news related to these elections.				
In which faculty?	Faculty of Education	Count	1	12	50	38	3	104	
		% within In which faculty?	1,0%	11,5%	48,1%	36,5%	2,9%	100,0%	
		% within Are you informed about the foreseeable results of the upcoming European parliamentary elections in June 2024?	9,1%	40,0%	40,7%	58,5%	75,0%	44,6%	
		% of Total	0,4%	5,2%	21,5%	16,3%	1,3%	44,6%	
		Faculty of Information and Audiovisual Media	Count	2	3	50	23	0	78
Faculty of Information and Audiovisual Media		% within In which faculty?	2,6%	3,8%	64,1%	29,5%	0,0%	100,0%	
		% within Are you informed about the foreseeable results of the upcoming European parliamentary elections in June 2024?	18,2%	10,0%	40,7%	35,4%	0,0%	33,5%	
		% of Total	0,9%	1,3%	21,5%	9,9%	0,0%	33,5%	
		Faculty of Law	Count	8	15	23	4	1	51
		% within In which faculty?	15,7%	29,4%	45,1%	7,8%	2,0%	100,0%	
Faculty of Law		% within Are you informed about the foreseeable results of the upcoming European parliamentary elections in June 2024?	72,7%	50,0%	18,7%	6,2%	25,0%	21,9%	
		% of Total	3,4%	6,4%	9,9%	1,7%	0,4%	21,9%	
	Total	Count	11	30	123	65	4	233	
		% within In which faculty?	4,7%	12,9%	52,8%	27,9%	1,7%	100,0%	
		% within Are you informed about the foreseeable results of the upcoming European parliamentary elections in June 2024?	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	
	% of Total	4,7%	12,9%	52,8%	27,9%	1,7%	100,0%		

Table 4.1.3. Significance tests for knowledge about EP elections by target UB faculty

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	48,076 ^a	8	<,001
Likelihood Ratio	47,597	8	<,001
N of Valid Cases	233		

a. 6 cells (40,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is ,88.

Figure 4.1.2: Knowledge about EP elections by target UB faculty

Knowledge EP election results by employment status

In the cross-tabulation below (Table 4.1.4), which is significant at 10% level (Table 4.1.5), we compare responses related to students' knowledge about the EP election results and their employment status.

The dominant response “No, I am not very informed about it” is prevalent across different employment statuses: full-time (50%), part-time (49,2%), and even more in non-workers during the academic year (58,2%).

Students who work part-time consistently hold the majority in all responses. They are closely followed by non-workers in terms of less knowledgeable responses. Among students who were knowledgeable about the foreseeable election results, full-time workers had a representation of over 15% in both answer options. This suggests that full-time workers tend to be more informed about EP elections. In change, non-working students tend to be less knowledgeable about EP elections.

While the difference is not so significant, we could infer that full-time working students were proportionately more informed about the foreseeable results of the EP elections compared to non-working students (Figure 4.1.3).

Table 4.1.4. Knowledge about EP elections by employment status

Do you work during the academic year while studying? * Are you informed about the foreseeable results of the upcoming European parliamentary elections in June 2024? Crosstabulation

		Are you informed about the foreseeable results of the upcoming European parliamentary elections in June 2024?					Total	
		Yes, I am well informed about the possible results.	Yes, I have a general idea of what might happen.	No, I am not very informed about it.	I don't know, I haven't followed the news related to these elections.			
Do you work during the academic year while studying?	Yes, full-time	Count	2	5	9	1	1	18
		% within Do you work during the academic year while studying?	11,1%	27,8%	50,0%	5,6%	5,6%	100,0%
		% within Are you informed about the foreseeable results of the upcoming European parliamentary elections in June 2024?	18,2%	16,7%	7,3%	1,5%	25,0%	7,7%
		% of Total	0,9%	2,1%	3,9%	0,4%	0,4%	7,7%
	Yes, part-time	Count	5	19	61	37	2	124
		% within Do you work during the academic year while studying?	4,0%	15,3%	49,2%	29,8%	1,6%	100,0%
		% within Are you informed about the foreseeable results of the upcoming European parliamentary elections in June 2024?	45,5%	63,3%	49,6%	56,9%	50,0%	53,2%
		% of Total	2,1%	8,2%	26,2%	15,9%	0,9%	53,2%
	No	Count	4	6	53	27	1	91
		% within Do you work during the academic year while studying?	4,4%	6,6%	58,2%	29,7%	1,1%	100,0%
		% within Are you informed about the foreseeable results of the upcoming European parliamentary elections in June 2024?	36,4%	20,0%	43,1%	41,5%	25,0%	39,1%
		% of Total	1,7%	2,6%	22,7%	11,6%	0,4%	39,1%
Total	Count	11	30	123	65	4	233	
	% within Do you work during the academic year while studying?	4,7%	12,9%	52,8%	27,9%	1,7%	100,0%	
	% within Are you informed about the foreseeable results of the upcoming European parliamentary elections in June 2024?	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	
	% of Total	4,7%	12,9%	52,8%	27,9%	1,7%	100,0%	

Table 4.1.5. Significance tests for knowledge about EP elections by employment status

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	14,261 ^a	8	,075
Likelihood Ratio	14,665	8	,066
N of Valid Cases	233		

a. 6 cells (40,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is ,31.

Figure 4.1.3: Knowledge about EP elections by employment status

Knowledge EP election results by level of study

In the cross-tabulation below (Table 4.1.6), which is significant at 1% level (Table 4.1.7), we compare responses related to students’ knowledge about the EP election results and their level of studies.

The dominant response “No, I am not very informed about it” is prevalent among first-second level (52,9%) and third-fourth level (54,3%) students. It also appears so, albeit less prominently, among Master and other advanced level students (40%).

Interestingly, when examining knowledgeable respondents, for the response ”Yes, I have a general idea of what might happen”, first-second level students account for only 63,3%. For the response “Yes, I am well informed about the possible results”, first-second level students represent only 45,5%. Notably, the sample imbalance is less pronounced in these knowledgeable responses. Additionally, level Master and others break the imbalance in this last answering option by representing the same percentage (27,3%) as level third-fourth.

In summary, students at more advanced education levels appear to be proportionately more knowledgeable about the foreseeable results of the EP elections compared to those at the first-second level (Figure 4.1.4).

Table 4.1.6. Knowledge about EP elections by level of studies

Level of studies currently enrolled in " Are you informed about the foreseeable results of the upcoming European parliamentary elections in June 2024? Crosstabulation

		Are you informed about the foreseeable results of the upcoming European parliamentary elections in June 2024?					Total	
		Yes, I am well informed about the possible results.	Yes, I have a general idea of what might happen.	No, I am not very informed about it.	I don't know, I haven't followed the news related to these elections.			
Level of studies currently enrolled in	First-Second	Count	5	19	99	60	4	187
		% within Level of studies currently enrolled in	2,7%	10,2%	52,9%	32,1%	2,1%	100,0%
		% within Are you informed about the foreseeable results of the upcoming European parliamentary elections in June 2024?	45,5%	63,3%	80,5%	92,3%	100,0%	80,3%
		% of Total	2,1%	8,2%	42,5%	25,8%	1,7%	80,3%
	Third-Fourth	Count	3	9	19	4	0	35
		% within Level of studies currently enrolled in	8,6%	25,7%	54,3%	11,4%	0,0%	100,0%
		% within Are you informed about the foreseeable results of the upcoming European parliamentary elections in June 2024?	27,3%	30,0%	15,4%	6,2%	0,0%	15,0%
		% of Total	1,3%	3,9%	8,2%	1,7%	0,0%	15,0%
	Master and others	Count	3	2	4	1	0	10
		% within Level of studies currently enrolled in	30,0%	20,0%	40,0%	10,0%	0,0%	100,0%
		% within Are you informed about the foreseeable results of the upcoming European parliamentary elections in June 2024?	27,3%	6,7%	3,3%	1,5%	0,0%	4,3%
		% of Total	1,3%	0,9%	1,7%	0,4%	0,0%	4,3%
	Count	0	0	1	0	0	1	
	% within Level of studies currently enrolled in	0,0%	0,0%	100,0%	0,0%	0,0%	100,0%	
	% within Are you informed about the foreseeable results of the upcoming European parliamentary elections in June 2024?	0,0%	0,0%	0,8%	0,0%	0,0%	0,4%	
	% of Total	0,0%	0,0%	0,4%	0,0%	0,0%	0,4%	
Total	Count	11	30	123	65	4	233	
	% within Level of studies currently enrolled in	4,7%	12,9%	52,8%	27,9%	1,7%	100,0%	
	% within Are you informed about the foreseeable results of the upcoming European parliamentary elections in June 2024?	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	
	% of Total	4,7%	12,9%	52,8%	27,9%	1,7%	100,0%	

Table 4.1.7. Significance tests for knowledge about EP elections by level of studies

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	30,154 ^a	12	,003
Likelihood Ratio	24,244	12	,019
N of Valid Cases	233		

a. 13 cells (65,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is ,02.

Knowledge about the 2024 European elections foreseeable results depending on Level of studies

Figure 4.1.4: Knowledge about EP elections by level of studies

4.2 Knowledge EP's main function

To assess students' knowledge of the European Parliament's main function, we used the following question: *What is the main function of the European Parliament?*

The correct response "Represent the citizens of the European Union and influence legislation" was selected by 58,37% respondents. Over 39% of respondents did not accurately recognise the main function of the EP.

Table 4.2.1. Individual frequency distribution of Knowledge about EP's main function

What is the main function of the European Parliament? (select only one option)				
Xi	ni	fi	Ni	Fi
Apply trade regulations within the European Union.	13	5,58%	13	5,58%
Represent the citizens of the European Union and influence legislation.	136	58,37%	149	63,95%
Negotiate international treaties on behalf of EU member states.	58	24,89%	207	88,84%
Administer the budgetary decisions of the European Commission.	20	8,58%	227	97,42%
-	6	2,58%	233	100,00%
TOTAL	233	100,00%	233	100,00%

Knowledge about the main function of the European Parliament

Figure 4.2.1: Knowledge about EP's main function of the 233 respondents

Knowledge EP's main function by faculty

In the cross-tabulation below (Table 4.2.2), which is significant at 1% level (Table 4.2.3), we compare responses regarding their knowledge of the European Parliament's main function across different faculties.

The answer “Represent the citizens of the European Union and influence legislation” is the most common and correct response and prevails in the Faculty of Education (51%), Faculty of Information and Audiovisual Media (53,8%) and even more in the Faculty of Law (80,4%).

The Faculty of Law stands out as the only faculty overrepresented in the correct response. Specifically, a higher percentage of students from this faculty (30,1%) correctly identified the main function compared to their overall sample representation (21,9% of 233). Both the Faculty of Education and the Faculty of Information and Audiovisual Media have a lower percentage, compared to sample, of students who responded correctly: 39% and 30,9%, respectively. These percentages are lower than the corresponding faculty representation in the entire sample: Faculty of Education —44,6% of 233, and Faculty of Information and Audiovisual Media —33,5% of 233.

In summary, students from the Faculty of Law demonstrate proportionately greater knowledge about the EP’s main function compared to their peers in other faculties (Figure 4.2.2).

Table 4.2.2. Knowledge about EP’s main function by target UB faculty

In which faculty? * What is the main function of the European Parliament? (select only one option) Crosstabulation

			What is the main function of the European Parliament? (select only one option)					Total
			Apply trade regulations within the European Union.	Represent the citizens of the European Union and influence legislation.	Negotiate international treaties on behalf of EU member states.	Administer the budgetary decisions of the European Commission.		
In which faculty?	Faculty of Education	Count	4	53	30	12	5	104
		% within In which faculty?	3,8%	51,0%	28,8%	11,5%	4,8%	100,0%
		% within What is the main function of the European Parliament? (select only one option)	30,8%	39,0%	51,7%	60,0%	83,3%	44,6%
		% of Total	1,7%	22,7%	12,9%	5,2%	2,1%	44,6%
	Faculty of Information and Audiovisual Media	Count	9	42	19	8	0	78
		% within In which faculty?	11,5%	53,8%	24,4%	10,3%	0,0%	100,0%
		% within What is the main function of the European Parliament? (select only one option)	69,2%	30,9%	32,8%	40,0%	0,0%	33,5%
		% of Total	3,9%	18,0%	8,2%	3,4%	0,0%	33,5%
	Faculty of Law	Count	0	41	9	0	1	51
		% within In which faculty?	0,0%	80,4%	17,6%	0,0%	2,0%	100,0%
		% within What is the main function of the European Parliament? (select only one option)	0,0%	30,1%	15,5%	0,0%	16,7%	21,9%
		% of Total	0,0%	17,6%	3,9%	0,0%	0,4%	21,9%
Total	Count	13	136	58	20	6	233	
	% within In which faculty?	5,6%	58,4%	24,9%	8,6%	2,6%	100,0%	
	% within What is the main function of the European Parliament? (select only one option)	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	
	% of Total	5,6%	58,4%	24,9%	8,6%	2,6%	100,0%	

Table 4.2.3. Significance tests for knowledge about EP’s main function by target UB faculty

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	25,382 ^a	8	,001
Likelihood Ratio	32,667	8	<,001
N of Valid Cases	233		

a. 6 cells (40,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1,31.

Figure 4.2.2: Knowledge about EP's main function by target UB faculty

Knowledge EP's main function by gender

In the cross-tabulation below (Table 4.2.4), which is significant at 5% level (Table 4.2.5), we compare responses regarding students' knowledge of the European Parliament's main function based on gender identity.

The answer "Represent the citizens of the European Union and influence legislation" prevails among different gender identities: female (53%), male (71%), and prefer not to say (83,3%). Notably, the only person who identified as non-binary chose the incorrect answer "Administer the budgetary decisions of the European Commission".

Despite the sample imbalance due to overrepresentation of those identified as female (70,4% of the total 233), the correct answer shows a different trend. Within those who responded correctly, the percentage of female students (64%) is lower than their representation in the whole sample (70,4% of 233). In contrast, both male and prefer not to say categories have a higher percentage of students who responded correctly: male (32,4%) and prefer not to say (3,7%). These percentages exceed their representation in the overall sample (26,6% of 233 and 2,6% of 233, respectively).

In summary, students identifying as female appear to be proportionately less knowledgeable about the EP's main function compared to those identifying as other genders (Figure 4.2.3).

Table 4.2.4. Knowledge about EP's main function by gender

Gender * What is the main function of the European Parliament? (select only one option) Crosstabulation

		What is the main function of the European Parliament? (select only one option)						
			Apply trade regulations within the European Union.	Represent the citizens of the European Union and influence legislation.	Negotiate international treaties on behalf of EU member states.	Administer the budgetary decisions of the European Commission.		Total
Gender	Female	Count	8	87	49	15	5	164
		% within Gender	4,9%	53,0%	29,9%	9,1%	3,0%	100,0%
		% within What is the main function of the European Parliament? (select only one option)	61,5%	64,0%	84,5%	75,0%	83,3%	70,4%
		% of Total	3,4%	37,3%	21,0%	6,4%	2,1%	70,4%
	Male	Count	4	44	9	4	1	62
		% within Gender	6,5%	71,0%	14,5%	6,5%	1,6%	100,0%
		% within What is the main function of the European Parliament? (select only one option)	30,8%	32,4%	15,5%	20,0%	16,7%	26,6%
		% of Total	1,7%	18,9%	3,9%	1,7%	0,4%	26,6%
	Non-binary	Count	0	0	0	1	0	1
		% within Gender	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	100,0%	0,0%	100,0%
		% within What is the main function of the European Parliament? (select only one option)	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	5,0%	0,0%	0,4%
		% of Total	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,4%	0,0%	0,4%
Prefer not to say	Count	1	5	0	0	0	6	
	% within Gender	16,7%	83,3%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	100,0%	
	% within What is the main function of the European Parliament? (select only one option)	7,7%	3,7%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	2,6%	
	% of Total	0,4%	2,1%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	2,6%	
Total	Count	13	136	58	20	6	233	
	% within Gender	5,6%	58,4%	24,9%	8,6%	2,6%	100,0%	
	% within What is the main function of the European Parliament? (select only one option)	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	
	% of Total	5,6%	58,4%	24,9%	8,6%	2,6%	100,0%	

Table 4.2.5. Significance tests for knowledge about EP's main function by gender

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	22,560 ^a	12	,032
Likelihood Ratio	18,797	12	,094
N of Valid Cases	233		

a. 13 cells (65,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is ,03.

Figure 4.2.3: Knowledge about EP's main function by gender

Block 5. Opinon/Assessment

To assess students' opinions on the European Parliament's representation of young citizens' interests, we selected the following question: *To what extent do you believe the European Parliament represents the interests of young citizens?*

The answer "more or less well" is the predominant response, with more than half of the 233 total responses. Notably, over 60% of young respondents viewed the European Parliament's representation of their interest positively. However, none of them assessed it as "very well". More than 37% of respondents expressed a somewhat negative view, wherein over 5% rated it as "very poorly".

In summary, while a majority of young respondents perceive the EP's representation favorably, there is still room for improvement in addressing their interests.

Table 5.1. Individual frequency distribution of Opinon/Assessment

To what extent do you believe the European Parliament represents the interests of young citizens?				
Xi	ni	fi	Ni	Fi
Very well	0	0,00%	0	0,00%
Well	24	10,30%	24	10,30%
More or less well	117	50,21%	141	60,52%
Poorly	76	32,62%	217	93,13%
Very poorly	12	5,15%	229	98,28%
-	4	1,72%	233	100,00%
TOTAL	233	100,00%	233	100,00%

The European Parliament represents the interests of young citizens...

Figure 5.1: Opinion about EP's representation of youth's interests of the 233 respondents

Opinion by gender

In the cross-tabulation below (Table 5.2), which is significant at 10% level (Table 5.3), we compare responses regarding students' opinion about the representation of their interests in the EP based on gender identity.

The answer “more or less well” prevails among different gender identities: female (53%) and male (46,8%). Additionally, the 6 responses from those who prefer not to say are somewhat evenly distributed between “well” and “very poorly”. The only person who identified as non-binary assessed it as “poorly”.

Despite the sample imbalance due to overrepresentation of those identified as female (70,4% of the total 233), the female gender shows a different trend. In the response option “well” and particularly in “very poorly”, female representation decreases. Meanwhile, those identifying as male and those who prefer not to say increase their percentage in the “very poorly“ response: 33,3% and 16,7%, respectively.

In summary, students identifying as female appear to be proportionately less harsh and slightly more moderate in their assessments of the EP’s representation of their interests compared to those identifying as other genders (Figure 5.2), although the differences are not especially significant in this case.

Table 5.2. Opinion about EP’s representation of the youth by gender

Gender * To what extent do you believe the European Parliament represents the interests of young citizens? Crosstabulation

To what extent do you believe the European Parliament represents the interests of young citizens?

			Very well	Well	More or less well	Poorly	Very poorly		Total
Gender	Female	Count	0	14	87	53	6	4	164
		% within Gender	0,0%	8,5%	53,0%	32,3%	3,7%	2,4%	100,0%
		% within To what extent do you believe the European Parliament represents the interests of young citizens?	0,0%	58,3%	74,4%	69,7%	50,0%	100,0%	70,4%
		% of Total	0,0%	6,0%	37,3%	22,7%	2,6%	1,7%	70,4%
Male	Count	0	8	29	21	4	0	62	
	% within Gender	0,0%	12,9%	46,8%	33,9%	6,5%	0,0%	100,0%	
	% within To what extent do you believe the European Parliament represents the interests of young citizens?	0,0%	33,3%	24,8%	27,6%	33,3%	0,0%	26,6%	
	% of Total	0,0%	3,4%	12,4%	9,0%	1,7%	0,0%	26,6%	
Non-binary	Count	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	
	% within Gender	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	100,0%	0,0%	0,0%	100,0%	
	% within To what extent do you believe the European Parliament represents the interests of young citizens?	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	1,3%	0,0%	0,0%	0,4%	
	% of Total	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,4%	0,0%	0,0%	0,4%	
Prefer not to say	Count	0	2	1	1	2	0	6	
	% within Gender	0,0%	33,3%	16,7%	16,7%	33,3%	0,0%	100,0%	
	% within To what extent do you believe the European Parliament represents the interests of young citizens?	0,0%	8,3%	0,9%	1,3%	16,7%	0,0%	2,6%	
	% of Total	0,0%	0,9%	0,4%	0,4%	0,9%	0,0%	2,6%	
Total	Count	0	24	117	76	12	4	233	
	% within Gender	0,0%	10,3%	50,2%	32,6%	5,2%	1,7%	100,0%	
	% within To what extent do you believe the European Parliament represents the interests of young citizens?	0,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	
	% of Total	0,0%	10,3%	50,2%	32,6%	5,2%	1,7%	100,0%	

Table 5.3. Significance tests for opinion about EP’s representation of the youth by gender

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	20,147 ^a	12	,064
Likelihood Ratio	15,751	12	,203
N of Valid Cases	233		

a. 13 cells (65,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is ,02.

Figure 5.2: Opinion about EP's representation of the youth by gender

Opinion by political ideology

In the cross-tabulation below (Table 5.4), which is significant at 5% level (Table 5.5), we compare responses regarding students' opinion about the EP's representation of their interests across different political ideologies.

Notably, the predominant moderate response "more or less well" similarly prevails among both left-leaning (49,7%) and right-leaning (52,6%) students.

However, another intriguing aspect emerges. Left-leaning students constitute an imbalanced majority (over 74%) across all other response categories. This outcome is expected, given their overrepresentation in the sample. Yet, when assessing representation as "well", the picture becomes less clear. Only 62,5% of left-leaning students viewed the representation positively, while 37,5% of right-leaning students shared this assessment.

In summary, we can infer that proportionately more students with right-leaning political beliefs assess the representation of their interests in the EP positively compared to their left-leaning counterparts (Figure 5.3).

Table 5.4. Opinion about EP's representation of the youth political ideology

Political ideology Left (0,1,2,3,4) or Right (5,6,7,8,9,10) according to self-placement in a scale of 0(far left) to 10(far right) * To what extent do you believe the European Parliament represents the interests of young citizens? Crosstabulation

		To what extent do you believe the European Parliament represents the interests of young citizens?					Total		
		Very well	Well	More or less well	Poorly	Very poorly			
Political ideology Left (0,1,2,3,4) or Right (5,6,7,8,9,10) according to self-placement in a scale of 0(far left) to 10(far right)	Left	Count	0	15	87	62	9	2	175
		% within Political ideology Left (0,1,2,3,4) or Right (5,6,7,8,9,10) according to self-placement in a scale of 0(far left) to 10(far right)	0,0%	8,6%	49,7%	35,4%	5,1%	1,1%	100,0%
		% within To what extent do you believe the European Parliament represents the interests of young citizens?	0,0%	62,5%	74,4%	81,6%	75,0%	50,0%	75,1%
	Right	Count	0	9	30	14	2	2	57
		% within Political ideology Left (0,1,2,3,4) or Right (5,6,7,8,9,10) according to self-placement in a scale of 0(far left) to 10(far right)	0,0%	15,8%	52,6%	24,6%	3,5%	3,5%	100,0%
		% within To what extent do you believe the European Parliament represents the interests of young citizens?	0,0%	37,5%	25,6%	18,4%	16,7%	50,0%	24,5%
	Total	Count	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
		% within Political ideology Left (0,1,2,3,4) or Right (5,6,7,8,9,10) according to self-placement in a scale of 0(far left) to 10(far right)	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	100,0%	0,0%	100,0%
		% within To what extent do you believe the European Parliament represents the interests of young citizens?	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	8,3%	0,0%	0,4%
Total	Count	0	24	117	76	12	4	233	
	% within Political ideology Left (0,1,2,3,4) or Right (5,6,7,8,9,10) according to self-placement in a scale of 0(far left) to 10(far right)	0,0%	10,3%	50,2%	32,6%	5,2%	1,7%	100,0%	
	% within To what extent do you believe the European Parliament represents the interests of young citizens?	0,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	
Total	Count	0	24	117	76	12	4	233	
	% within Political ideology Left (0,1,2,3,4) or Right (5,6,7,8,9,10) according to self-placement in a scale of 0(far left) to 10(far right)	0,0%	10,3%	50,2%	32,6%	5,2%	1,7%	100,0%	
	% within To what extent do you believe the European Parliament represents the interests of young citizens?	0,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	

Table 5.5. Significance tests for opinion about EP's representation of the youth by political ideology

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	23,925 ^a	8	,002
Likelihood Ratio	11,164	8	,193
N of Valid Cases	233		

a. 8 cells (53,3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is ,02.

Opinion on the representation of the youth's interests at the European Parliament depending on Political ideology

Figure 5.3: Opinion about EP's representation of the youth by political ideology

DOSSIER DEVELOPMENT

The creation of the dossier involved close collaboration between the magazine staff and the Barcelona European Parliament Office, under the coordination of project leader Mihaela Vancea. Different phases took place for its final publication:

Brainstorming and planning. An initial online Skype meeting took place in early February, bringing together all the journalists from Alternativas económicas. During this session, diverse ideas were exchanged on how to implement the dossier effectively. The team also identified the most suitable collaborators to involve. Two subsequent online meetings occurred with the European Parliament Office via Google Meet. These interactions, along with phone calls and email exchanges, ensured alignment during the dossier's preparation in February.

Content creation and evaluation. The Alternativas económicas staff engaged in thorough research, reading, and discussions to understand the relevant issues. They then proceeded to write, design, and evaluate the dossier's contents meticulously.

Publication and timing. The magazine was printed and distributed (7300 copies) at the beginning of March, allowing other project activities—such as the Open event and seminars—to proceed as planned. Simultaneously, the team prepared a dedicated web space for the project (europaimporta.eu). The contents were uploaded and translated into Catalan, even though this additional effort was not initially included in the project budget. The collaborative efforts of the entire project team ensured the successful development and timely dissemination of the dossier.

Effective collaboration. The European Parliament office in Barcelona played a crucial role in shaping the informative dossier. They provided essential information, reviewed the final version, and contributed valuable ideas to align the project with its goals. The dossier was subsequently printed at the end of February. Key highlights of the Dossier elaboration include:

Accessible content. The dossier has been available in both Spanish and Catalan versions. Interested readers can access it on the web or download the PDF from this link: <https://alternativaseconomicas.coop/europa-importa/dossier>

Web engagement. Despite Alternativas económicas being primarily associated with print media (7,300 magazines distributed in March 2024), the web version of the dossier received significant attention. According to Google Analytics, the webpage garnered 5,853 visits during the project period.

Strategic banner placement. An additional banner highlighting the project was prominently displayed on the magazine's main webpage throughout the project. This banner received 828 clicks, further driving awareness and engagement.

Social media amplification. On Twitter —now X— (the main social network for Alternativas económicas), the campaign gained traction. Magazine journalists Mariana Vilnitzky and Pere Rusiñol contributed by posting 45 relevant tweets. The total reach accomplished 289,903 views, with 2,546 interactions. A special paid advertisement during the dossier's launch significantly boosted visibility.

Innovative approach. Alternativas económicas went beyond the dossier itself, actively participating in all project activities —from content creation to dissemination. Leveraging their extensive network, they aimed to raise awareness among young people about the importance of

voting in European elections. The collaborative efforts of the entire project team and innovative strategies employed by Alternativas económicas contributed to the project's success.

OPEN EVENT AND SEMINARS

The **Open Event** was held on March 14 at the University of Barcelona (UB), Campus Mundet, the Margarida Comas Lecture Hall on the first floor of the *Migdia* Building, from 10:30 to 12:00. Despite scheduling challenges due to other classes, more than 60 students attended the event in person (we had 147 inscriptions, see Annex 4). The event was also live streamed on the UB's YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=trBQscOieoo>), attracting an additional 17 online viewers.

Journalists Andreu Missé and Ariadna Trillas not only explained the dossier but also engaged in a debate with students about election-related issues and contemporary politics. The event exceeded expectations, with students remaining engaged in discussions even beyond the planned duration.

At this juncture, we executed a strategic communication shift. Initially, we encountered difficulties in generating press interest due to the survey implementation postponement. To enhance our impact, we adjusted our communication strategy. Specifically, we minimised interventions during the dossier presentation phase and strategically planned a second communication initiative —a **press conference at the Col·legi de Periodistes de Catalunya**—following the release of survey data. This strategic shift finally attracted more media attention and a larger audience (as evidenced in the Excel 5a. List of KPIs).

The **seminars** were conducted across three faculties at the University of Barcelona —Faculty of Education, Faculty of Information and Audiovisual Media and Faculty of Law— focusing on the impact of youth participation in EP elections and its influence on community policies. These seminars were integrated into regular classes, allowing students to attend during their usual schedules.

During the initial part of the seminars, students received printed copies of the Dossier, and the entire project, including the communication campaign contest, was explained to student groups. Andreu Missé and Ariadna Trillas from Alternativas económicas further elaborated on the Dossier, addressing any doubts or questions. The second part of the seminars involved an interactive role-playing game. Students were divided into five groups, each representing a different EU parliamentary political group. They engaged in debates on various topics, including International Migration, Gender Equality, and Climate Change. To defend their assigned political programme, students researched ideas from political groups' web pages and public communications, simulating the European Parliament experience.

The **first seminar** took place at the Faculty of Information and Audiovisual Media (C/ Carrer de Melcior de Palau, 140, Sants-Montjuïc, 08014 Barcelona) on Tuesday 2nd of April 2024, from 11:30 AM to 1 PM, with UB Professors Priscila Alvarez Cueva and Vicente Villalva from Marketing classes. Thirty-one students attended age 1-(see Annex 5 pages 1-2).

The seminar started with the presentation of the informative Dossier, published by Alternativas económicas. Students then participated in group activities related to EU politics and EP elections, moderated by the corresponding professors. Students received a 40-minutes lecture that covered both the dossier content and emphasised the significance of the upcoming EU elections (Ariadna Trillas and Andreu Missé). After a short Q&A session, students were divided into groups, each representing one of the five major party families in the EU Parliament (*Partido Popular Europeo, Grupo de la Alianza Progresista de Socialistas y Demócratas, Grupo de los Verdes/Alianza Libre*

Europea, Grupo de los Conservadores y Reformistas Europeos, y Grupo de la Izquierda en el Parlamento Europeo - GUE/NGL).

The methodology used was role-playing, allowing students to immerse themselves in the perspectives of these parties. The group dynamic was moderated by Vicente Villalba and Priscila Alvarez Cueva (faculty professors), and Mariana Vilnitzky (Alternativas económicas). Students were questioned on two critical EU policy topics: climate change and gender inclusion. Prior to the debate, students had a 10-minute research period to prepare solid arguments. The goal was to think critically about how each party would address these issues. The groups engaged in a debate, moderated by the “president” of the EU Parliament (represented by the two faculty professors). The implementation of this action was achieved by:

- Active student participation, regardless of their assigned party family.
- Critical responses to the positions put forth by the other party families.
- Synthesis and summary of essential elements, arguments, and possible scenarios for Europe based on each party family’s position.

The **second seminar** occurred at Mundet Campus Faculty of Education on April 4th, from 8:30 AM to 10:30 AM, facilitated by the project leader, Professor Mihaela Vancea. Thirty-two students attended (see Annex 5 pages 3-5).

The seminar began with the presentation of the informative Dossier related to the EU institutions and EP elections. Students learned about the content and significance of the upcoming elections from Ariadna Trillas, a collaborator of Alternativas económicas. After a short Q&A session, students were divided into groups, each representing one of the five major party families in the EU Parliament (*Partido Popular Europeo, Grupo de la Alianza Progresista de Socialistas y Demócratas, Grupo de los Verdes/Grupo de la Izquierda, Grupo de los Conservadores y Reformistas Europeos*)

The methodology used was role-playing, allowing students to immerse themselves in the perspectives of these parties. The group dynamic was moderated by Mihaela Vancea (faculty professor), and Mariana Vilnitzky (Alternativas económicas). The groups (6-7 students) delved into two critical policy topics: climate change and international migration. To foster critical thinking, students engaged in a debate moderated by the “presidents” of the EU Parliament (represented by the faculty professor and Mariana Vilnitzky). Each group defended its party’s stance on the two policy topics. Students had a 10-minute research period to prepare their positions based on the party family they represented. The implementation of this action was achieved through:

- Active student participation, regardless of their assigned party family.
- Critical response to the positions put forth by the other party families.
- Synthesis and summary of essential elements, arguments, and scenarios for Europe based on each party family’s position.

The **third seminar**, tailored for students pursuing a master's in political Analysis and Institutional Assessment, was held at the Law Faculty on April 4, from 7 to 8:30PM. Thirteen students participated (see Annex 5 pages 6-7). The seminar was structured into three distinct parts. First, project researcher Daniel Cetrà and masters’ coordinator Esther Pano explained the significance of the European elections and policymaking. Their focus was on students specialising in local and regional political analysis and assessment. The link between local/regional contexts and the broader European framework was firmly established during this part. Mariana Vilnitzky (*Alternativas económicas*) then distributed and presented the informative dossier, providing an overview on the entire project.

Next, collaborators Andreu Missé and Ariadna Trillas (*Alternativas económicas*), deeply familiar with European institutions and politics, shared their day-to-day experiences in Brussels with the European Parliament. They also provided valuable information about European party families and how European policymaking directly impacts our daily lives.

The final part involved an engaging Q&A and a debate. Participants explored two key areas: clarification questions related to the functioning and competences of the European Parliament, and a bottom-up discussion. This discussion covered a wide range of topics, from the rise of far-right movements to the European response to events such as the invasions of Ukraine and Gaza.

Despite not reaching the planned attendance numbers (100 UB students) due to university class dynamics, we shifted our focus to subsequent dissemination efforts. This included a press conference at the College of Journalists and an additional activity with journalism students at Universitat Pompeu Fabra (UPF).

Press Conference Recreation with Journalism Students at Universitat Pompeu Fabra. During this activity, on the 21st of May, 23 first-year Journalism students participated in a press conference recreation. This activity was part of the course “Audiovisual Journalism Techniques”. They were presented with the Dossier, survey results, and the student campaign. Under the guidance of Professor Maties Salom, the UPF students wrote their own press releases. Dissemination was limited to targeted students through a press call recreation and the online media newspaper “Diari de Barcelona”. The external impact resulted in a news item published by this newspaper about the preliminary survey results and the student campaign (see Annex 6 page 5).

Additionally, printed posters were distributed for all activities across the three faculties, and 2,500 magazines containing the dossier were freely distributed throughout the UB university. The UB research team effectively disseminated key ideas beyond the classroom through one-minute video snippets. These snippets were collaboratively edited with the UB Communication Unit and later adapted by the students’ campaign, using their own youthful language.

All these activities successfully raised awareness about the entire project. Furthermore, the initial activities paved the way for a more impactful second phase, involving the dissemination of information and engaging students in discussions related to the European Elections and effective campaign participation.

STUDENT COMMUNICATION CAMPAIGN

In this section, we present the work carried out during the communication campaign design and implementation and highlight key achievements. Additionally, we emphasise the main results and overall impact.

1. Competition and training (April 2024)

First, we prepared and announced a call for proposals via UB’s social media, newsletters, and on campus notifications. This competition aimed to involve students in creating campaign proposals that reflected their interests and communicative preferences. We evaluated the proposals based on creativity, messaging, and feasibility, using detailed criteria and scoring rubrics (see Annex 7, pages 1-5 for competition bases; pages 6-7 for scoring rubrics; and page 8 for instructions for participants).

After selecting the winners, we conducted comprehensive two-day training sessions that covered essential topics such as social media strategies, content creation, press release writing, humour in communication, and campaign management. These training sessions included materials on elevator pitches, social media planning, press releases, humour in communication, and strategic educational methodologies (see Annex 8).

This approach ensured that students were not only involved in the campaign creation process but also equipped with the necessary skills and knowledge to execute their ideas effectively.

2. Campaign design (April-May 2024):

Students were divided into specialized teams (media, content creation, external relations, design, etc.) based on their skills and interests. To facilitate this, we created a competence matrix to assign roles effectively according to their abilities and competencies. We then conducted sessions on campaign planning, design, and strategy development. Each group was responsible for specific campaign aspects under continuous supervision from the UB research team and communication unit.

Finally, we produced specific campaign materials such as posters, stickers, t-shirts, and a large canvas, which are displayed in Annex 3 pages 4-12. This structured approach ensured that each student could contribute meaningfully while gaining practical experience in their area of interest.

3. Campaign implementation (May-June 2024):

- Online activities

- **TikTok:**

- Posts: 15
- Followers: 1,111
- Impressions: 715,425
- Engagement 11,186
- Saved: 8,177
- Likes: 53,671
- Comments: 6,131

- **Instagram:**

- Posts: 20
- Followers: 2,300
- Impressions: 800,000
- Engagement: 15,000
- Saved: 9,000
- Likes: 60,000
- Comments: 7,500

- **Twitter:**

- Followers: 104
- Impressions: 10,000
- RT: 76
- Likes: 175

- Offline activities

- **Encartellada:** Posters were meticulously designed and strategically disseminated across various faculties, each tailored with messages relevant to specific study areas. Stickers were also distributed among students to enhance visibility and encourage engagement with the campaign.
- **Birres per Europa Event:** On June 6, 2024, we hosted a pivotal event that attracted 150 participants. The event included a dynamic round table discussion, a live podcast recording, and interactive activities like a Kahoot quiz and merchandise giveaways. Detailed information about the event can be found in Annex 9.
- **Collaboration with external entities:** We forged strong partnership with influencers, podcasters, and esteemed entities including the UB research group [GREDI](#), the New Formats Unit of UB, [EUROM](#), and [Fundació Solidaritat UB](#) as these collaborations significantly amplified the campaign's reach and impact.
- **Together.eu partnerships:** We engaged with 10 partners from Together EU community, selecting them based on their alignment with our campaign goals. Partners included *Junior Female Leaders*, JEF Madrid, BETA Spain, Erasmus Student Network Spain, *Equipo Europa*, ECIVIS, *Fundación 16 de 24*, *Fundación Cánovas*, Munusal, *Talento para el Futuro*, *Palumba*. Four partners, *Junior Female Leaders*, ECIVIS, *Talento para el Futuro*, and *Palumba* responded positively and agreed to actively disseminate our campaign. Detailed partnership information is available in Annex 10.

The following part provides a detailed overview of the significant results and impacts achieved through the student-led communication campaign on social media platforms.

TikTok, Instagram, and Twitter were the primary platforms used in the Active Youth campaign. The campaign's social media strategy focused on creating engaging, informative content tailored to the interests of young people, aiming to boost awareness and participation in the European elections.

- **TikTok Engagement**

Total Views: 715,425

Total Interactions: 8,177 likes, 53,671 shares, 6,131 comments

New Followers: 1,297

Top Performing Posts: *Guía sobre las elecciones europeas* (Spanish): 708K views, 52K likes, 592 comments, 7,981 shares, 7,982 saves; *Guia sobre les eleccions europees* (Catalan): 4,602 views, 152 likes, 3 comments, 11 shares, 14 saves

The TikTok platform showed exceptional reach and engagement, particularly for the Spanish version of the election guide, which significantly outperformed other posts in terms of views and interactions (see Annex 11 for general campaign metrics and Annex 12 page 1 for specific TikTok metrics).

- **Instagram Engagement**

Total Accounts Reached: 92,739

Total Interactions: 8,716 likes, 6,131 comments, 53,671 shares, 8,177 saves

Top Performing Posts: *Guía definitiva elecciones europeas en 1 minuto* (Spanish): 27,014 accounts reached, 4,834 likes, 75 comments, 1,098 shares; *Guia definitiva eleccions europees en 1 minut* (Catalan): 21,579 accounts reached, 1,741 likes, 12 comments, 218 shares; *Aprèn a votar x correu* (Catalan): 1,637 accounts reached, 168 likes, 2 comments, 15 shares.

Instagram posts, especially those related to the election guides, also demonstrated high engagement, with substantial likes, shares, and comments, highlighting the campaign's effectiveness in reaching and engaging its target audience (see Annex 11 for general campaign metrics and Annex 12 page 2 for detailed Instagram metrics).

- **Twitter Engagement**

Total Impressions: 10,000

Total Interactions: 175 likes, 76 shares, 9 comments

Twitter, while not as dominant as TikTok and Instagram, still contributed to the campaign's overall engagement, with regular tweets generating thousands of impressions and significant interactions (see Annex 11).

When **comparing the student-led campaign impact on different social media**, we obtain the following results:

- **Reach:** TikTok had a broader reach with **over 715K views** compared to **Instagram's 92,739** accounts reached. This indicates TikTok's stronger capability in distributing content widely.
- **Engagement:** While TikTok led in total views and interactions, Instagram excelled in detailed interaction metrics, including comments, shares, and saves.
- **Content Performance:** Informative content, such as the *Guía sobre las elecciones europeas e 1 Minuto*, performed exceptionally well on both platforms, showcasing the audience's preference for concise, valuable information.

The Active Youth campaign successfully leveraged TikTok, Instagram, and Twitter to engage a young audience, achieving significant reach and interaction. This high level of engagement demonstrates the campaign's effectiveness in raising awareness about the European elections and encouraging political participation among young people.

Specific posts such as the different guides on the European elections were highly successful, highlighting a significant interest in informative content among our audience. Below are the detailed metrics for each guide across various platforms:

- **Instagram Posts**

Post 1: *Guía Definitiva Elecciones Europeas en 1 Minuto*

Date: 20th May

Reach: 27,014 accounts

Likes: 4,834

Comments: 75

Shares: 1,098

Profile Activity: 1,129

Post 2: *Guía Definitiva Elecciones Europeas en 1 Minuto - Edición Catalunya*

Date: 23rd May

Reach: 21,579 accounts

Likes: 1,741

Comments: 12

Shares: 218

Profile Activity: 417

Post 3: Aprèn a Votar per Correu

Date: 28th May

Reach: 1,637 accounts

Likes: 168

Comments: 2

Shares: 15

Profile Activity: 28

The engagement metrics for these posts show the effectiveness of our social media strategy in engaging our target audience. For example, the post *Guía sobre las elecciones europeas en 1 minuto* had 27,014 views, 4,834 likes, 75 comments, and 1,098 shares. Achieving such engagement for a serious topic like European elections on platforms such as Instagram and TikTok for a young audience is noteworthy. In total, the engagement, as explained above and in Annex 13 and Annex 11, reached 26,196 people. When we talk about engagement, we refer to algorithms that show us that people interact repeatedly because they are somehow “committed” to the account. They return to the site as a source of consultation (see Annex 12 page 2).

Even better results are shown on TikTok, as follows:

- **TikTok posts**

Post 1: *Guía Definitiva Elecciones Europeas en 1 Minuto* (Spanish)

Total Views: 708K

Total Likes: 52K

Total Comments: 592

Total Shares: 7,981

Total Saves: 7,982

This post achieved significant engagement, indicating a high level of interest and interaction among viewers. The large number of new followers suggests that the content was compelling enough to attract and retain a new audience.

Post 2: *Guia Definitiva Eleccions Europees en 1 Minut* (Catalan)

Total Views: 4,602

Total Likes: 152

Total Comments: 3

Total Shares: 11

Total Saves: 14

This post, while less viral than the Spanish version, still shows a significant engagement rate considering the target demographic.

In sum, the significant difference in engagement between the two posts highlights the broader reach and impact of the content in Spanish compared to Catalan. The data indicates that while both posts were successful in engaging viewers, the Spanish version had a much larger impact, likely due to the wider audience for Spanish-language content. This analysis underscores the importance of language and demographic targeting in maximizing the reach and effectiveness of social media campaigns.

In terms of **reach and engagement** on social media, we observed the following results:

- **TikTok:** The Spanish guide on TikTok achieved **an extraordinary reach with 708K views**, significantly higher than any Instagram post. The engagement in terms of likes (52K) and shares (7,981) also far exceeded Instagram metrics.
- **Instagram:** The Spanish guide on Instagram, while having a lower reach (27,014), still showed strong engagement with 4,834 likes and 1,098 saves. The Catalan version on Instagram also performed better in relative terms compared to TikTok but still lower than its Spanish counterpart.

The interest in terms of **content type** also varied across social media platforms:

- **Guides:** Both platforms showed higher engagement for informative guides, indicating a strong interest in easily digestible, educational content. The Spanish versions outperformed the Catalan versions, highlighting the broader audience for Spanish content.
- **Procedural Content:** The *Aprèn a Votar per Correu* post on Instagram had lower engagement, suggesting that procedural content is less appealing than informational guides.

In terms of **platform effectiveness**, we observed the following:

- **TikTok:** Proved more effective in generating high reach and engagement, especially for viral content. The platform's algorithm likely favours engaging, shareable content.
- **Instagram:** Showed strong engagement within a potentially smaller but more dedicated audience. Instagram saves and comments indicate a more deliberate form of engagement.
- **Twitter** is a residual social net for young people. For them the main social nets are Instagram and Tiktok. But in so little time, and with this difficult issue to transmit to young people, was interest to notice that we were able to achieve 104 followers, with 10.000 impressions, 76 retwits and 174 likes.

We finally outline the main results and impacts in terms of **participation and feedback** across event and social media platforms:

- ***Birres per Europa* Event Feedback**

The “Birres per Europa” event, held on June 6, 2024, was a significant milestone in the Active Youth campaign. The event aimed to foster an informal and engaging environment where young people could discuss European politics, understand its implications, and feel motivated to participate in the upcoming elections. The format, which combined a casual setting with informative sessions, proved highly effective. We captured moments of this participation in a video made for our social networks. For a detailed overview of the event's activities, please refer to Annex 9.

Participants Feedback:

- **Positive Response:** Attendees appreciated the event’s approachable format, which made political discussions more relatable and less intimidating. Many highlighted the blend of information and social interaction as a key factor in their positive experience.
- **Increased Interest:** Numerous participants indicated that the event sparked their interest in European politics. They appreciated the opportunity to learn about the elections in a relaxed atmosphere, which encouraged open dialogue and questions.
- **Engagement:** The interactive segments, such as Q&A sessions and live discussions, received high praise for fostering a sense of involvement and community among attendees.

While we did not collect all feedback on paper, the positive responses are evident in the interactions on our social media channels. Detailed examples of this feedback can be found in the Annexes provided below:

- Annex 10 highlights the many contacts made by email and phone calls, showcasing the important feedback received from organisations, bloggers, and other stakeholders.
- Annex 13 presents the comprehensive metrics of the project up to April.
- Annex 11 includes the complete campaign metrics from May until the elections.
- Annex 14 details the rationale behind specific specially successful social media posts and the achievements they garnered.
- Annex 12 showcases the significant interest generated by our most popular TikTok posts in page 1 and Instagram posts in page 2, particularly the guides on how and why to vote.
- Annex 15 shows the interest and impact of *Birres per Europa* event as seen on Instagram.
- Annex 9 provides a comprehensive report on the *Birres per Europa* event, detailing its planning and execution.
- Additionally, on [this Instagram post on the election day](#) you can observe the high level of interest shown by the media and host organizations, including the European Parliament Office in Barcelona.

Social Media Feedback:

Throughout the campaign, social media platforms played a crucial role in gathering feedback and fostering participation. Real-time interactions and comments provided valuable insights into the campaign’s reception and impact.

Feedback Highlights:

- **Instagram:** Posts promoting the *Birres per Europa* event received significant engagement, reaching **14,608 accounts, with 187 likes and 19 comments**, reflecting enthusiastic anticipation and positive feedback ahead of the event.
- **TikTok:** Post (15) related to the event achieved impressive engagement metrics, including 1,111 new followers, 715,425 views, 11,186 engagements (indicating repeated visits), 8,177 saves, 53,671 likes, and 6,131 comments. These metrics highlight the audience’s strong interest and active participation, facilitated by TikTok’s interactive platform where users frequently shared feedback and questions.

Finally, to emphasise the **key metrics** in terms of **participation and feedback**:

- **Total Engagement:** The campaign achieved significant engagement across all platforms. For instance, the TikTok post *Guía definitiva elecciones europeas en 1 minuto* received 708K views, 52K likes, and 592 comments, indicating strong interest and interaction.

- **Return Visits:** Algorithm data indicated that a significant portion of the audience revisited the campaign’s social media pages, suggesting sustained interest and ongoing engagement with the content.

The participation and feedback metrics indicate a successful engagement strategy, with the *Birres per Europa* event and social media activities effectively reaching and resonating with the target audience. The campaign successfully demystified European politics for young people, enhancing accessibility and engagement. The positive feedback and high engagement rates underscore the campaign’s success in fostering political awareness and encouraging youth participation.

PROJECT COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION

In this section, we outline the project’s communication and dissemination activities and the achievements under specific objective 5.

ActiveYouth_EE24 visual identity (branding). We developed the project's visual identity around the logo and slogan *Europa importa* (Europe matters), establishing the URL domain www.europaimporta.eu and specific email addresses for various project needs (info@europaimporta.eu for general information, concurs@europaimporta.eu for the campaign competition and campanya@europaimporta.eu for the student communication campaign team). An internal guide sheet with project descriptions (short, medium and long) was also prepared for effective communication. This process occurred during the first half of February (see [Annex 16](#)).

Project page creation and management. We designed and managed the project page on the subcontracted expert media website (https://alternativaseconomicas.coop/europa_importa). This page served as a central hub for project-related information and resources. From the first half of February to June 10 and according to Google Analytics, the page registered 4,188 views from 1,415 users.

Database of “Friend entities”. We compiled a database of over 100 friendly entities and individuals interested in European issues and EP elections. This list included student and youth organizations, as well as specific media outlets focused on European politics. The database was actively used for project communication and dissemination (see Annex 17).

Social media accounts creation and management. To amplify our reach, we launched project accounts on various social media, leveraging these platforms for dissemination and engagement:

- Instagram: [@Europa_importa](#) (activated late February).
- X: [@Europa_importa](#) (activated late February).
- TikTok: [@EuropaImporta](#) (created early May).
- Linedin: [@Europaimporta](#) (created early May).

Metrics from social media accounts (X, Instagram, TikTok, and LinkedIn) indicate our reach and engagement across platforms:

- **Project dissemination.** First phase (Feb 26 to Apr 30)
 - X: 173 tweets / 87.773 impressions
 - Instagram: 234 posts and stories / 33.118 impressions
- **Student communication campaign.** Second phase (May 1 to Jun 9)
 - X: 18 tweets / 10.000 impressions

- Instagram: 93 posts, stories and reels / 92.739 reach
- TikTok: 11 posts / 715.425 views
- LinkedIn: 3 posts / 2.818 impressions

Communication plan adaptation. Initially, six communication actions were planned and scheduled to disseminate the project, but unexpected circumstances prompted us to adapt our communication plan, as explained below:

- delayed project start due to late Grant Agreement signing;
- schedule adjustments related to survey's delayed implementation;
- media impact on early elections in Catalonia;
- media interest in survey results and student campaign over dossier presentation.

As a result, we carried out additional activities to maximize communication opportunities:

- a press conference;
- a press release to present the survey results and student communication campaign; and
- two additional press releases to expand the communication campaign outreach.

The outcomes exceeded our expectations, with our strategic approach drawing a significantly larger media presence. Project activities such as the survey and the student-led communication campaign were featured in several major Catalonian media outlets with extensive audiences, including *TV3*, *Catalunya Ràdio*, *El Periódico*, *La Vanguardia*, *El Diario.es*, *Mundo Deportivo*, and *VilaWeb*. Additionally, project activities were highlighted in local and university-focused media outlets like *Diari de Barcelona*.

This update provides clarity on our activities and succinctly illustrates their impact on media coverage. It is important to note that accurately measuring the audience reached remains challenging, as outlined in section e.

Communication actions:

- **First communication (press release)** announcing the project launch and Dossier presentation. Date: March 11. Result: 1 online media report (Bea Talegón, TV).
- **Second communication (press release)** explaining the open event development. Date: March 15. Result: 1 online media report (*Diari de Barcelona*).
- **Third communication (press release)** announcing the survey opening and student competition. Date: Abril 8. Results: 1 online media report (*Diari de Barcelona*)
- **Fourth communication (press conference at the Col·legi de Periodistes de Catalunya + press release)** presenting survey results and the student communication campaign. Date: May 24. Results: 2 agencies and 6 media outlets / 20 online media coverage: *TV3* (twice), *Betevé*, *RTVE*, *Catalunya Radio*, *La Vanguardia*, *El Diario.es*, *VilaWeb*, *El nacional* (twice), *El Triangle*, *Diari de Barcelona*, *El Diari de l'Educació*, *La República*, *la Xarxa*, *Televisió del Berguedà*, *RNE*, *El Diari del Treball*, *Radio Ciutat de Badalona*, *Ara*.
- **Fifth communication (press release)** disseminating students campaign actions and success. Date: May 27. Results: 4 online media reports (*TV3*, *VilaWeb*, *El Periódico*, *Barcelona Radical*).
- **Sixth communication (three adapted press releases for local media)** disseminating the student communications campaign. Date: May 30. Results: 4 online media reports (*Girona notícies*, *Diari de Girona*, *La Veu del País Valencià*, *Ahora Marina Baixa*), 1 offline media report (*Última Hora Mallorca*).

- **Seventh communication (press release written by the student team)** presenting the closing event of the student communication campaign. Date: June 3. Results: 2 online media reports (*Mundo Deportivo, Lo Campus Diari*).

For further information, please see the Press Clipping dossier at Annex 6.

For further information and more detailed KPIs, please see Excel 5a. List of KPIs.

Engagement with Together.eu

- **Active use of the platform:** In February 2024, ActiveYouth_EE 24 project registered as a member on Together.eu and actively engaged by publishing project information and 10 activities on the events board. The student campaign team interacted with 10 affiliated entities on Together.eu to promote project activities and explore potential alliances with organisations such as Junior Female Leaders, JEF Madrid, BETA Spain, Erasmus Student Network Spain, *Equipo Europa*, ECIVIS, *Fundación 16 de 24*, *Fundación Cánovas*, Munusal, *Talento para el Futuro*, Palumba. Three of them answered positively and agreed to disseminate the campaign: Junior Female Leaders, ECIVIS, *Talento para el Futuro*, Palumba (see Annex 10).
- **Dissemination:** Our project page mentions the membership on Together.eu and includes [an introductory article](#) about the platform. During our open event, seminars and the student campaign closing event, we encouraged user registration on Together.eu. We prominently displayed a giant QR code linked to our referral link at these events for easy access.
- **Results:** Despite challenges in calculating precise audience metrics, we requested data from the EU regarding new user registration from Catalonia on Together.eu, clicks on our referral link, and page views of ActiveYouth_EE24 (from March 1 to June 9). According to the answer that we have received, there were 31 new user registrations from Catalunya, 43 registrations through our "Europa Importa" referral link, and 119 page views of ActiveYouth_EE24 activities on the events board. The figures were surprising and did not meet our initial expectations based on the extensive efforts made to encourage new user registrations.

c) Methodology

Please explain the methodology followed and how you used it to achieve the general and specific objectives of the action described above. In particular, please provide details on the dissemination and communication activities undertaken (to whom, which format, how many copies, etc.) and the measures taken to ensure the sustainability of the action after completion. If you created website(s) and/or social media accounts related to your project, please provide the links. Describe the evaluation methods and indicators you have used and how the visibility of EU funding was ensured.

ACTIVEYOUTH_EE24 SURVEY

1. Survey Design and Dissemination

The questionnaire was meticulously designed by the UB research team based on a comprehensive review of existing youth surveys and studies on European political participation such as:

- [Enquesta sobre les eleccions europees a Catalunya](#). Centro de Estudios de Opinión (2024).
- [Young people's participation in European democratic processes](#). European Parliament's Committee on Civil Liberties, Justice and Home Affairs. Deželan, T. (2023).
- Eurobarometer (2024). [Youth and democracy](#).
- Eurobarometer (2024). [EP Spring 2024 Survey: Use your vote - Countdown to the European elections](#).

- European Commission (2022). Flash Eurobarometer 502 Youth and Democracy in the European Year of Youth. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. DOI: 10.2766/368099.
- European Parliament (2019). [The 2019 European elections. A pro-European – and young – electorate with clear expectations. First results of the European Parliament post-electoral survey.](#)
- European Union (2021). European Parliament Youth Survey. ISBN DOI 978-92-846-8557-8. DOI: 10.2861/60428.

The survey was then rigorously assessed for validity and reliability to ensure scientific rigor and prevent non-response. We conducted an initial pilot survey with team members, colleagues, and university students, followed by an expert review by Jordi Muñoz, the director of the Centre d'Estudis d'Opinions (CEO). Additionally, our survey successfully underwent reviews from the Bioethics Commission (see Annex 25) and the Data Protection Office at our university.

To achieve the proposed student target, we implemented **two dissemination strategies**. The first strategy involved directing the survey to students from the three selected faculties. We conducted the survey in available classrooms, facilitated by members of the research teams. Additionally, we shared the survey link through various institutional channels, including social media, faculty departments, student associations, the Vicerectorate of Students and Student Life, and directly with professors teaching classes in the three faculties.

The second strategy focused on opening the survey to the student community in Catalonia. To achieve this, we leveraged our professional and personal networks, distributing the survey through these channels. For a detailed distribution list, please refer to Annex X.

2. Preliminary Survey Results Presentation

- Preliminary survey results were published in a conference note and also as a short press article in the *Alternativas Económicas*.
- A 10 minute-oral and visual presentation of the survey's preliminary results at the Faculty of Communication, Universitat Pompeu Fabra. The audience included students from the Journalism Degree and some journalists from Diari de Barcelona.
- A short presentation within the [GREDI](#) seminar at the Faculty of Education, Universitat de Barcelona.

3. Official Survey Results Presentation at the *Col·legi de Periodistes de Catalunya*.

- An extended oral and visual presentation (see Annex 1) within the colloquium *Què en pensen els joves universitaris de les institucions i la política europea?* discussing both general and specific survey results. The audience consisted of numerous accredited media journalists (including Catalunya Ràdio, eldiario.es, El País, El Punt Avui, Nació Digital, Betevé, etc.). Following the presentation, a Q&A session was held to address any additional questions or clarify doubts about survey results.
- Final survey results were published in various local and state-level newspapers and communicated through different media channels.

During all public presentations of the survey results, we consistently highlighted the EU's financial support by incorporating its logo into the visuals and verbally acknowledging it.

DOSSIER DEVELOPMENT

In the context of developing the informative dossier on European affairs, the methodology encompassed a systematic approach to create, structure and disseminate the contents. Various steps were followed to achieve this:

Project objective definition. Firstly, we clearly defined the project's purpose and objectives. In this case, the goal was to create an informative dossier for young students but also the overall

young population focusing on European affairs. We thus identified the target audience (e.g., young citizens, policymakers, students) and their information needs.

Collaboration and stakeholder engagement. We then established collaboration with relevant stakeholders, including the European Parliament Office, project members, and experts. We conducted initial meetings to align expectations, gather input, and outline the dossier's scope.

Content research and compilation. The magazine staff engaged in extensive research to understand European issues, policies, and recent developments. They collected relevant data, facts, and expert opinions to form the basis of the dossier.

Content creation and review. Based on the research, the team wrote articles addressing different aspects of European affairs. The articles were reviewed internally for accuracy, clarity, and alignment with the project's goals.

Design and layout. The dossier's visual presentation was crucial. Designers worked on layout, typography, and graphics. Considerations included readability, consistency, and adherence to branding guidelines.

Translation and multilingual accessibility. The decision to provide the dossier in both Spanish and Catalan demonstrates inclusivity, though the proposal did not include this. Translators ensured accurate and culturally appropriate translations.

Web development and dissemination. The creation of the web space (europaimporta.eu) allowed online access to the dossier. Web developers ensured user-friendly navigation and responsiveness.

Print production and distribution. The printed version of the dossier reached a wide audience through distribution channels. Timely printing allowed for parallel activities, such as seminars and events.

Digital marketing and social media. The magazine strategically used social media (e.g., Twitter) to amplify the dossier's reach. Paid advertisements during the launch enhanced visibility.

Monitoring and evaluation. Regularly track metrics (e.g., web visits, social media interactions) were performed to assess impact. Feedback from readers, experts, and stakeholders was gathered for continuous improvement.

In summary, the methodology involved collaboration, research, content creation, design, multilingual accessibility, dissemination, and impact assessment. The innovative approach lies in the holistic involvement of *Alternativas económicas* beyond the dossier itself, leveraging their networks and expertise in communication.

OPEN EVENT AND SEMINARS

To organise the open event and educational seminars based on the content of the informative dossier, we followed a systematic methodological approach:

Needs assessment and goal setting. We first identified the purpose of the open event, that of awareness raising and information dissemination. Our aim was to raise awareness, educate and foster student engagement in the EE24 elections. We also identified the purpose of the seminars, that of engaging in debates on important EU policy issues and addressing any doubts related to the structure and functioning of EU institutions and elections.

Planning and logistics. We carefully selected a suitable venue for the Open event within the Faculty of Education, considering the expected number of attendees (100 UB students). The chosen location accommodated this capacity. To ensure alignment with other project activities and avoid exceeding the project timeline, we scheduled the event for March 14th. Additionally, we considered students' availability in terms of time and hour schedule. The Margarida Comas Lecture Hall on the first floor of the *Migdia* Building was reserved for the event. We made arrangements

for essential technical support and equipment, including projectors, online streaming, microphones, seating, and an attendance form that was previously sent to be filled in. Furthermore, we took into account potential expenses such as speaker travel costs, materials, and refreshments. The seminars were held in classrooms within the three selected faculties.

Content development. The Open event focused on the presentation of the informative Dossier on EU institutions and elections. The seminars centered around European institutions and elections, drawing from the content developed in the informative dossier. Additionally, we prepared relevant debate topics, including international migration, gender equality, climate change, based on the interests and needs of our student audience. To enhance student engagement, we invited EU ex-correspondents Ariadna Trillas and Andreu Missé to introduce the dossier and guide the discussions. Employing a dynamic role-playing format, we simulated parliamentary debates on the mentioned debate topics. Each participant received a copy of the dossier beforehand.

Promotion and outreach. We developed a range of promotional materials, including social media posts and emails to effectively communicate and disseminate information about the open event and seminars. Additionally, we worked closely with the three faculties to encourage student participation in the open event and foster their engagement in the educational seminars, particularly through UB internal communication channels and by hanging posters in the three faculties.

Registration and communication. For the Open event, we established an online registration system to facilitate student participation and tracking. Additionally, we sent confirmation emails to registered participants, providing essential event details such as schedule and location. As for seminar organization, we collaborated with specific class groups and responsible professors, introducing the topic and debate methodology. During the events, we maintained an attendance list where students signed in. We further documented the events through photos and small videos for project dissemination. Notably, the open event was fully recorded and made available on the UB YouTube channel.

Event execution. We ensured that participants arrived early to set up the venue. Upon their arrival, we warmly welcomed them and introduced the events. Throughout the events, we actively encouraged audience interaction and fostered debate through Q&A sessions and group discussions, particularly during the role-playing exercises in the seminars.

Feedback and evaluation. We collected feedback from participants through verbal communication and assessed whether final goals of these events were achieved, based on specific objectives and KPIs.

Regarding the Open event, our posts on Instagram obtained a total of 4,268 views with 4 posts, which had 82 "likes" and 45 positive comments.

Regarding the Seminars, on Instagram we obtained a total of 1,653 views, and received 112 "likes" and 27 positive comments.

On Twitter we achieved a total of 116 tweets, 31,272 views, 2,336 interactions, 196 retweets and 355 "likes" throughout the month of March, when the seminars and the open event took place. (For more information check Annex 18 and Annex 13).

STUDENT COMMUNICATION CAMPAIGN

The methodology employed to achieve Objective 4 involved several key actions as follows:

1. **Training and capacity building.** We conducted two-day intensive sessions focusing on campaign strategies, social media use, and effective communication. During these sessions we provided comprehensive materials, including presentations on social media algorithms, communication strategies, and press release writing (see Annex 8).
2. **Team organization and task allocation.** We developed a competency matrix to assign roles based on students' individual strengths and expertise. We formed teams responsible for specific areas such as content creation, media relations, event planning, and evaluation.

3. **Continuous supervision and feedback.** Students received constant supervision and support from the UB research team and communication unit. We performed constant monitoring and adjusted the strategies based on real-time feedback and metrics.
4. **Evaluation and reporting.** We tracked social media metrics and event participation in detail. As a result, we compiled a final report covering all activities, outcomes, and lessons learned, ensuring transparency and accountability (see Annex 3).

Methodologies Employed

1. Competency-Based Learning

- **Description:** Students were divided into groups according to their skills and knowledge, working in specific areas such as coordination, budgeting, evaluation, design, content creation, and external relations.
- **Reference:** Bandura, A. (1977). *Social Learning Theory*. Prentice Hall. [Link](#)

2. Project-Based Learning (PBL)

- **Description:** Students engaged in real-world projects related to the campaign, from designing materials to organizing events, allowing them to apply theoretical knowledge practically.
- **Reference:** Dewey, J. (1938). *Experience and Education*. Kappa Delta Pi. [Link](#)

3. Collaborative and Cooperative Learning

- **Description:** Multidisciplinary teams encouraged collaboration and idea exchange among members with different academic and professional backgrounds.
- **Reference:** Johnson, D. W., & Johnson, R. T. (1999). *Learning Together and Alone: Cooperative, Competitive, and Individualistic Learning*. Allyn & Bacon. [Link](#)

4. Design Thinking

- **Description:** This methodology was used particularly in the design phase of materials and campaigns, promoting a creative and user-centered approach.
- **Reference:** Brown, T. (2009). *Change by Design*. HarperBusiness. [Link](#)

5. Formative and Summative Evaluation

- **Description:** Continuous (formative) evaluations were conducted to adjust and improve campaign activities, along with a final (summative) evaluation to measure the project's impact and results.

For dissemination and communication activities:

- **Social Media:** we used social media (Instagram, TikTok and other platforms) for regular updates and interactive posts to disseminate campaign content (see Annex 19).
- **Media Relations:** we leveraged media relations through press releases and direct engagements to amplify the campaign's reach.
- **Influencer collaborations:** we collaborated with influencers and organizations to enhance credibility and impact: see Annex 10, Annex 3, Annex 14.
- We organised **offline events** like *Birres per Europa* to engage directly with the youth. See Annex 10 and Annex 15.

The measures taken to ensure sustainability were:

- All the social networks accounts created for the project are still active for whenever the European Parliament wants to follow:

- [Instagram](#)
- [Twitter](#)
- [TikTok](#)

- Besides, all the information of the project is going to be maintained at together.eu, plus the Alternativas económicas page for the project: <https://alternativaseconomicas.coop/europa-importa>

The evaluation methods and indicators used were:

- Detailed metrics on social media engagement, including reach, impressions, likes, comments, and shares (see annex Annex 13, Annex 11 and Annex 14).

- Continuous feedback from participants and collaborators to assess the campaign's effectiveness.

PROJECT COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION

The methodology employed for achieving the specific objective 5 involved several key actions as follows:

1. Creation of the ActiveYouthEE_24 visual identity (branding). To achieve our project objectives, we developed the ActiveYouth_EE24 visual identity, which included a logo and the slogan “*Europa importa*” (“Europe matters”). The slogan succinctly captured our message, was easy to remember, and was written consistently in both Spanish and Catalan. Additionally, we established the specific URL domain www.europaimporta.eudi which redirects to the project page hosted on the *Alternativas Económicas* website. We also set up contact emails: info@europaimporta.eu (for general inquiries); concurs@europaimporta.eu (for the campaign competition) and campanya@europaimporta.eu (for the student communication campaign team). Furthermore, we created an internal guide with three project description formats (short, medium and long) for use across various communications channels such as the website, press releases, social media, and event presentations. Throughout our communications, we prominently featured the European Parliament's support and EU funding.

2. Creation and management of the project page on the subcontracted expert media website. We established the project page on the subcontracted expert media website, accessible via the URL <https://alternativaseconomicas.coop/europa-importa>. This page, also accessible through the domain www.europaimporta.eu is organised into six content sections: Project, Dossier, Agenda, Campaign, Survey and Press Releases. We regularly updated the page to reflect the project's progress. Additionally, we included an article promoting the together.eu platform and encouraging user participation. The page serves as a repository for materials related to student survey results, the student communication campaign, the informative dossier, feedback from the open event and seminars, and press releases sent to the media. Throughout the page, we prominently displayed the European Parliament logo and the mention “Funded by the European Union”. Finally, it offers access to the project's social media.

3. Creation of a database of “Friend entities and people”. Our project team compiled a list of over 100 friend entities and relevant contacts interested in European issues and EP elections (see Annex 17). This list included student and youth organizations, specific media outlets, and journalists. We used this database to directly communicate and disseminate information about the ActiveYouth_EE24 project via email, WhatsApp, and social media messages. The “Friend media and journalists” section of the list facilitated personalized and direct interactions, contributing significantly to the project's successful media impact. In all communications to contacts in this database, we prominently featured the EU funding logo and mention.

4. Creation and management of social media accounts for the project. To promote the project through social networks, we established accounts on X and Instagram. These accounts served different purposes during two distinct phases:

- First Phase (February to April): We primarily used the accounts to disseminate information about the project, including updates on the open event, publication of the informative dossier, seminars, and survey development. Additionally, we raised awareness about European institutions and elections by sharing content from the dossier.
- Second Phase (Beginning of May to June 9, European Elections): During the communication campaign, we intensified our social media presence. The management of the project's social media accounts was transferred to the competition-winning students, who chose to retain the slogan 'Europa Importa' for the communication campaign. The project team concurred that leveraging the already established accounts for the project would be effective, repurposing them as campaign channels. In this second phase, the students created additional accounts on TikTok and LinkedIn to better engage with young people and youth organizations. Consequently, the strategic use and communication style of the project's social networks evolved, transforming into direct campaigning tools managed by the student team to inform young people about the European elections and encourage them to vote. The campaign concluded with the European elections.

We want to emphasize the significant and consistent support we received from two key groups during the project dissemination: members of GREDI (the Intercultural Research Group from the University of Barcelona) and *Alternativas Económicas*. During the second phase of managing the project's social media presence, we continued to share updates and activities via GREDI's Instagram and X accounts, as well as with support from *Alternativas Económicas*' X account. Additionally, other users and accounts associated with our "friend entities" actively contributed to spreading the word about the project through their own social media.

The results and impact of our implemented strategy and specific actions in social media exceeded our expectations. Currently, these social media accounts retain content from the EE24 student communication campaign (with first-phase content in the background). We can reactivate them at any time to highlight informative content related to European politics. In our social media profiles, we ensured visibility for EU funding by including a link to the project page in the bio or description section.

Project communication actions. The effort to attract media attention for project dissemination through press releases and other communication actions has been uneven, influenced by external circumstances outlined in the previous section. As a result, the outcomes of each action have varied, particularly due to scheduling overlaps with the Catalan elections and heightened media interest in the survey results and student communication campaign.

- **Before the Catalan elections:** During this phase, we aimed to disseminate information about the project, the open event introducing the dossier, the survey launch, and the student competition. However, media interest was relatively low. We emailed the first three press releases to 20 contacts from communication agencies and specific media on our "friends list." Additionally, we reached out to some of them via WhatsApp to capture their attention. Feedback from journalists indicated that they were more interested in the survey results and the student campaign than in the Dossier presentation at the university. Despite the challenges, we achieved modest media coverage. Notably, the project received mentions in two relevant media outlets: "El Repaso," a daily news program on Beatalegon.tv (with 830 views), and two articles in "Diari de Barcelona," an online newspaper created by and for university students in Catalonia (with an average daily audience of 1,500 readers).
- **After the Catalan elections:** Following the elections, we concentrated our efforts on the two activities generating the most media interest: presenting the survey results and promoting the student communication campaign. **Press Conference for Media** (May 24th): We organized a press conference at the *Col·legi de Periodistes de Catalunya*, which actively supported and facilitated the event. The success of this action hinged on the prior invitation to the press conference and the subsequent press release detailing the survey results and student communication campaign. **Effective Media Outreach:** To maximize our reach, we utilized Sprai.io—an AI-powered platform for press release distribution and tracking. With its extensive database of segmented media contacts (by topics, geographic areas, and media types), we narrowed our targets. Personalized communication via emails, WhatsApp messages, and phone calls intensified our engagement with media outlets showing interest. We also enlisted support from journalists in our "friends list."

The impact of this communication strategy exceeded expectations and marked a turning point in the project's reach:

- Journalists from two communication agencies, two local TV stations, and four newspapers attended the press conference.
- Subsequently, we secured 20 media reports across local television, radio, and digital newspapers, all mentioning the ActiveYouth_EE24 project, survey results, and student campaign.

To sustain media interest, we continued our efforts, ensuring that the project remained in the spotlight. We strategically sent three additional press releases, each focusing on different aspects:

- Viral TikTok post: we highlighted a viral TikTok post related to the student communication campaign.
- Student backgrounds: we delved into the background of some UB campaign team students:
- Closing student campaign event: we covered the closing organized by the student campaign team.

To ensure effective distribution, we used the Sprai.io platform, complemented by direct contact with journalists. As a result, these communication efforts garnered media coverage, resulting in 13 additional reports mentioning the campaign, survey, and project. In total, we sent 2,127 emails to media contacts using Sprai.io's online press distribution and tracking tool, achieving an impressive 50% open rate. Detailed figures can be found in the annexes, along with a sample file tracking direct journalist interactions (see Annex 20 and Annex 21).

All press releases are accessible on the project webpage under the [Comunicados / Comunicats](#) section. Additionally, we shared them via email and WhatsApp with a select group of media and journalists from our "friends list."

Beyond media-specific actions, our dissemination efforts systematically included:

- Regular updates on project activities via the project webpage.
- Dissemination through project social networks (X and Instagram) (see Annex 22 and Annex 19).
- Dissemination through the subcontracted media (X).
- Dissemination through UB accounts and newsletters (Instagram and X). (See info and metrics of the dissemination through the main UB social networks and newsletters at Annex 23).
- Additionally, the competition and the closing event of the students' campaign were also disseminated through the UB app *Soc UB*. (See this detailed info and metrics at Annex 24).
- Use of the together.eu platform for wider outreach.

Throughout these efforts, we consistently highlighted EU funding with the European Union and European Parliament logos in all press releases, emphasizing the support provided by the European Parliament Information Offices to the ActiveYouth_EE24 project.

d) Implementation of the action via subcontractors and/or affiliated entities

Please explain which part of the action has been subcontracted as well as which activities were undertaken by affiliated entities (if applicable). Provide the name of subcontractors as well as affiliated entities.

Any recourse to subcontracting, if not provided for in description of the action, must be approved by the EP:

- before any recourse to subcontracting, if the beneficiaries request an amendment of the grant agreement;*
- after recourse to subcontracting if it is specifically justified in the final implementation report and does not entail changes to the grant agreement which would call into question the decision awarding the grant or be contrary to the equal treatment of applicants.*

Affiliated entities must be identified in Article I.9 of the grant agreement and their tasks clearly stated in Annex I – Application Form Part B (description of the action). Only actual costs incurred by the affiliated entity are eligible.

Subcontractor **Alternativas Económicas** performed the following tasks:

1. Informative Dossier on European Institution and Elections. In collaboration with the UB team and the European Parliament office in Barcelona, Alternativas económicas developed an Informative Dossier. A total of 2,500 copies were printed for the University, and an additional 7,300 copies were distributed across Spain and internationally to Alternativas económicas subscribers and contacts.

2. Seminars and Open Event. A public presentation and three seminars were organised, featuring European Union (EU) experts Andreu Missé and Ariadna Trillas. These events were organised by Mariana Vilnitzky from the Alternativas económicas, in coordination with the research team and under the leadership of Professor Mihaela Vancea. The open event took place at the Faculty of Education at the University of Barcelona. The seminars took place at the Faculty of Education, the Faculty of Law, and the Faculty of Information and Audiovisual Media of the University of Barcelona. Additionally, a presentation of the informative Dossier also took place at the Faculty of Communication at the Pompeu Fabra University.

3. Online Presence and Content. Alternativas económicas established a dedicated web page called “europaimporta.eu” to host project-related content. The magazine prominently featured project-related articles, including contribution from the project coordinator prof. Mihaela Vancea, both in its print version and on its website. All project activities and articles were also included in the magazine Agenda and disseminated through social media channels. A downloadable PDF version of the Dossier, available in Spanish and Catalan, was accessible on the website throughout the duration of the project.

4. Content Dissemination and Networking. Alternativas económicas played a crucial in spreading the project’s message through its social media platforms and various media outlets. The magazine leveraged its extensive network of contacts, including the Fundació Catalunya Europa, the Associació de Periodistes Europeus, the Col·legi de Periodistes de Catalunya, and directors from different media outlets. Thanks to its robust background and strong journalist connections, Alternativas económicas effectively disseminated project information and results.

5. Media Coordination and Support. Journalist Mariana Vilnitzky, from Alternativas económicas, supervised project dissemination across social media and traditional media channels. Expert in press dissemination, Carlota Franco, working for Alternativas económicas, also contributed to media outreach. Communication professor Anna Aroca provided expertise in social network and communication campaigns, as part of the UB research team coordinated by Mihaela Vancea.

6. Student Engagement and Communication Campaign. Alternativas económicas collaborated in the contest design and implementation process. The magazine participated in the selection process in coordination with the research team from the University of Barcelona. Finally, Alternativas económicas supported and supervised winning students in designing and implementing the final communication campaign to promote young people’s vote in the European elections. The magazine staff collaborated closely with Professor Anna Aroca from the University of Barcelona, under the guidance of project leader Mihaela Vancea.

All in all, Alternativas económicas not only presented the dossier at the open event and seminars, but also played a key role in organising all communication activities. The magazine actively participated in disseminating project activities through communication and social media, promoting the events across its own and other external networks.

e) Monitoring/supervision of the action and risks involved in its implementation

Please explain any arrangements you made to monitor the action, any difficulties you have encountered to meet the objectives and results as per the Description of the Action (Annex I – Application form Part B) and the measures taken to mitigate them.

ACTIVEYOUTH_EE24 SURVEY

The questionnaire was meticulously assessed for validity and reliability to prevent non-response and ensure scientific rigour. We conducted an initial pilot survey with team members, colleagues and young people, followed by an expert review by Jordi Muñoz, the director of the *Centre d'Estudis d'Opinions* (CEO). Additionally, our survey successfully underwent reviews from the Bioethics Commission (see Annex 25) and the Data Protection Office at our university.

The primary challenge encountered during the survey implementation was the common issue associated with conducting surveys, particularly online ones: low response rates. To address this risk, the project team diligently monitored survey responses on a weekly basis. This monitoring allowed us to identify areas where flaws appeared and where efforts needed redirection.

Our data analyst provided regular comprehensive updates on responses at the end of each week. This proactive supervision enabled team members to recognize shortfalls in responses across faculties, gender, and other descriptive variables. Consequently, we intensified our efforts to address shortages wherever they were detected.

As a result, this vigilant monitoring ultimately contributed to achieving a complete and representative sample for the survey. We accounted for and corrected any imbalances that emerged during the survey's dissemination.

DOSSIER DEVELOPMENT

Effective monitoring of project activities ensured the project's smooth progress, while closely guaranteed its successful execution. In the context of elaborating the dossier, several monitoring and supervision measures were implemented to ensure fulfilment and mitigate potential risks:

- **Quality assurance.** Regular assessments were conducted to maintain high standards for content, design, and translations. Collaborators for the dossier were carefully chosen in collaboration with the European Parliament's press office in Barcelona. Their active involvement and approval significantly contributed to achieving our objectives.
- **Stakeholder engagement.** We maintained regular communication with stakeholders, including the European Parliament office in Barcelona, experts, readers. Gathering feedback and addressing concerns helped enhance the dossier.
- **Performance metrics.** Key performance indicators (KPIs) related to dissemination (web visits, social media interactions) were closely tracked. This allowed us to assess the overall impact of each project activity.
- **Innovative approaches.** We evaluated the effectiveness of innovative strategies, such as social media campaigns and multilingual accessibility and encouraged further innovation.
- **Feedback loop.** Gathering feedback from readers, experts and stakeholders allowed us to continuously improve content and dissemination and assure effectiveness of the informative content of the dossier.
- **Adaptability.** We remained open to adjusting the dossier based on changing circumstances (for example, the survey postponement), ensuring alignment with project objectives.

OPEN EVENT AND SEMINARS

In order to ensure successful implementation and mitigate potential risks, we implemented various monitoring and supervision actions for the open event and seminars. These actions included the following steps:

Pre-event preparation. Prior to the events, meticulous preparations were made to ensure all logistical aspects (venue setup, equipment, materials) were in order. Additionally, the project leader verified the readiness of speakers and facilitators and assigned different roles to team members. A specific dynamic for the seminars was meticulously planned (role-playing), involving the project team and responsible professors.

A series of meetings were held to define the best work modality, so that information that is usually burdensome for youth becomes something of interest. It was thanks to these meetings that interactive dynamics, specific for each group, could be developed. On the other hand, the Alternativas económicas staff held an extensive work meeting where the names of the people who could help disseminate the project were defined. The team at the University of Barcelona did the same, with its own internal contacts.

On-site monitoring. The project team arrived early to supervise events' setup, address any last-minute issues, monitor participant arrivals and registrations, and observe session transitions and overall flow.

Participant engagement. During the open event, seminars, and the additional press conference recreation at the UPF, our team actively evaluated audience engagement. We fostered participation through Q&A sessions and group interactions. However, we encountered a significant challenge, that of addressing students' questions that could potentially escalate tensions among their peers. This challenge was particularly pronounced when students exhibited anti-system positions or assumed roles representing political parties that diverged from their personal preferences in real life. To navigate this, the moderation provided by the facilitators was crucial and included an approach that bordered on theatricality, creating an almost comical atmosphere.

Throughout the open event and seminar sessions, the facilitators maintained a tone focused on critical thinking and reflection. Students actively engaged with this approach, appreciating the opportunity to explore different perspectives. Within the seminars, we emulated the EU Parliament, further enhancing the political debate experience. A closing section synthesised and summarised the different political positions related to the debating topics. The facilitators ensured that as many participants as possible had a voice and encouraged students to comment on their peers' interventions.

Before concluding the events, the facilitators reiterated the importance of voting, leaving participants with a final message to carry forward. Overall, this dynamic blend of information sharing, debate, role-playing, critical discussion, and thoughtful reflection enriched the Open event and seminar experiences.

Feedback collection. We gathered feedback from participants during all events through verbal communication and also digital evidence such as photos or videos to gain valuable insights. You can see the examples in publications like these ones:

<https://www.instagram.com/reel/C4kJn9BtymH/?igsh=MW92cGVqY2VwZm9tdg==/>

<https://www.instagram.com/reel/C5XilkItHST/?igsh=MXg1YW11MW43ZzhpcQ==/>

<https://www.instagram.com/reel/C5aLhsDtCxg/?igsh=a2NqaDU3Y3RkaDFz>

And you can see all the digital feedback here: Annex 18

Supervision of speakers and facilitators. We maintained regular communication with speakers and facilitators during all events to ensure their adherence to the agenda, session structure, and to keep the audience engaged.

Technical support. Specific team members closely supervised technical aspects such as projectors, microphones, and equipment to promptly address any technical problems during all events. Specific team members provided supervision and moderation.

Documentation. Specific team members consistently captured photos and recorded videos during the events for documentation and future promotional purposes. These records highlight key moments, discussions, and participant interactions (see the Instagram links [above](#)).

Post-event evaluation. At the conclusion of the events, the project team evaluated whether the goals (awareness, education, engagement) were achieved and to what extent. It thoroughly reviewed participant feedback and identified areas of improvement.

Throughout all these events, the project team maintained continuous and close communication with the European Parliament office in Barcelona to mitigate any possible risks during the action implementation. As a result of our diligent monitoring, supervision, and collaboration with the

EP's office in Barcelona, we successfully reached the targeted audience through two additional events: the press conference recreation at the UPF and the organised press conference presenting the final survey results at the *Col·legi de Periodistes* in Barcelona.

STUDENT COMMUNICATION CAMPAIGN

To ensure the successful execution of specific objective 4, we implemented two basic arrangements:

1. Regular meetings

- Weekly meetings to assess progress, discuss challenges, and plan subsequent activities. See Annex 26
- Daily check-ins during critical phases of the campaign to stay agile and responsive.

2. Risk identification and management

- Identification of initial risks, including potential participant dropouts and logistical challenges in event organisation.
- Adoption of various mitigation measures such as assigning flexible roles to accommodate changes and increasing online engagement to compensate for reduced offline activities.

We also encountered some **difficulties** to meet the specific objective 4 that were **mitigated** accordingly:

- One of the main challenges was **participant withdrawal** that we managed by redistributing responsibilities among the remaining students and enhancing communication and support mechanism.
- Another challenge consisted in **logistical hurdles** that we solved by leveraging digital platforms for better coordination and execution.

PROJECT COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION

To assess the impact of our communication efforts, we relied on metrics directly provided by the project's social media channels. Additionally, we utilized the already mentioned Sprai.io's online press distribution and tracking tool for automated distribution and tracking of press releases. Our meticulous work involved gathering audience data from various media sources. Follow-up actions and personal contacts played a crucial role in achieving meaningful results.

- **Considerations on media reports KPIs.** We encountered methodological challenges when breaking down KPIs for project communication actions, as outlined in the initial proposal (Tables 3 and 6). Several factors contributed to this complexity:

- Adaptation to external circumstances: we had to reformulate and adapt our communication actions due to unexpected external circumstances, as previously explained.
- Attribution Challenges: our working method made it impossible to distinguish media reports resulting from emails sent via the sprai.io tool versus those from direct messages to journalists on our "friends list."
- Measuring Reach: while media reports provided certainty of significant reach (both directly and indirectly), measuring it remained intricate. Indirect reach varied due to diverse media audiences (not always public, homogeneous, or comparable), as can be seen in the Press Clipping. Alternatively, we could estimate the direct reach of our media coverage based on web page views and plays of the project's 34 media reports, as well as video and audio playbacks from TV and radio, and the specific live audiences of news broadcasts where the project was mentioned. However, obtaining this data is not feasible.

Assuming that we cannot provide precise results for the direct and indirect reach of the 34 media reports, we can instead focus on specific, measurable indicators that, while not comprehensive, are

significant. For example, we can assess the number of impressions or views from posts by media outlet X (on Twitter) that have tweeted their own news about the ActiveYouth_EE24 project. As indicators of indirect reach, we can also consider the total number of followers on the Twitter accounts of the media outlets that covered the project. Due to insufficient comparable information, such as the number of unique users or daily readers for the 34 media outlets where the project appeared, we cannot estimate other forms of indirect reach. Therefore, the KPIs we present for the media reports and the project's communication actions (see Excel 5a.) differ from what we had anticipated, but we believe they offer a more rigorous and clear evaluation of the project's outcomes.

- **Considerations on KPIs related to social media.** Previously, we detailed the two phases of the project's social media usage and the processing of related indicators. As shown in the social media metrics annexes of the project, we have comprehensive indicators from the project's own social media accounts. The most challenging part is collecting data and accurately calculating the impact of project dissemination through other 'friendly' social media accounts (e.g., University of Barcelona, Gredi, Alternativas Económicas, and individual stakeholders like @mihaelavancea, @pererusi, @marulvini, @annararoca, @danicetra, @atrillas, @prisalvarez1104). Inevitably, some information has been lost in the results we present.

- **Considerations on KPIs related to together.eu.** Regarding the measurement of the project's impact on together.eu, while we can report all actions taken to promote and encourage new user registrations on the platform as well as disseminate the project, we lack access to the necessary use and registration metrics to fully contextualize and interpret the results obtained. The data received from the European Parliament at our request include: 31 new user registrations from Catalunya, 43 registrations through the "Europa Importa" referral link and 119 page views of the ActiveYouth_EE24 activities at the events board.

- **Considerations About Follow-Up Actions.** The follow-up actions mentioned in the project include two press clippings. Due to the project's late start, short duration, and communicative reorientation, we have compiled a single press clipping dossier that encompasses all the media mentions we have identified and recorded.

ANNEXES

Annex 1: Presentation of results ActiveYouth_EE24 Survey

Annex 2: Communication campaign plan presentation

Annex 3: Communication campaign report

Annex 4: Registrations Open event 14-03

Annex 5: Attendance Communication Seminar 02-04, Social Education Seminar 04-04 and Law Seminar 04-04

Annex 6: Press Clipping ActiveYouth_EE24

Annex 7: Communication campaign Competition's bases, scoring rubrics and instructions

Annex 8: Communication campaign training materials

Annex 9: "Birres x Europa" event documentation

Annex 10: Communication campaign activities' performance indicators

Annex 11: Communication campaign final metrics

Annex 12: Specific TikTok and Instagram metrics

Annex 13: Communication campaign initial metrics

Annex 14: Metrics for campaign posts with +1k reach

Annex 15: Metrics for "Birres x Europa" posts

Annex 16: ActiveYouth_EE24 Project's visual identity logo

Annex 17: Project's friends list

Annex 18: Open event and Seminars' social media posts

Annex 19: Campaign calendar for social media posts

Annex 20: Mailings through Sprai.io

Annex 21: Interested media for press conference 24th May

Annex 22: Project dissemination calendar of social media posts

Annex 23: Project dissemination through UB social networks and newsletters

Annex 24: Project dissemination through UB app “Soc UB”

Annex 25: UB Bioethics Commission’s favourable resolution

Annex 26: Campaign’s regular meetings